

Optical Characterization of Highly Efficient Nanostructured Solar Cells

Thesis Submitted to Faculty of Science-Ain Shams
University in partial fulfillment for Degree of
Master in Physics

By

Amr Hisham Khalaf Mahmoud
B.Sc. in Physics 2014

Supervisors

Assoc.Prof

Dr. Hala Mohamed Hosny

Physics Department
Faculty of Science
Ain Shams University

Assoc.Prof

Dr. Mohamed Farahat Othman

Mathematics and Engineering Physics Department
Faculty of Engineering
Mansoura University

Assoc.Prof

Dr. Mohamed Hassan Abdel-Aziz

Basic Science Department
Faculty of computers and information Sciences
Ain Shams University

CERTIFICATION OF APPROVAL

Optical Characterization of highly efficient nanostructured solar cells

By

Amr Hisham Khalaf Mahmoud

Signature

Assoc.Prof

Dr Hala Mohamed Hosny

Physics Department
Faculty of Science
Ain Shams University

.....

Assoc.Prof

Dr Mohamed Hassan Abdel-Aziz

Basic Science Department
Faculty of computers and information Sciences
Ain Shams University

.....

Assoc.Prof

Dr Mohamed Farahat Othman

Mathematics and Engineering Physics Department
Faculty of Engineering
Mansoura University

.....

Optical Characterization of highly efficient nanostructured solar cells

Name: Amr Hisham Khalaf Mahmoud

Degree: M.Sc

Department: Physics

Faculty: Science

University: Ain Shams

Graduation Date: 2014 - Ain Shams University

Registration Date: 3/2016

Grant Date: 2019

Contents

Acknowledgments	Vii
.....	
Abstract	ix
.....	
List of Publications	Xi
.....	
List of Symbols	xii
.....	
List of Abbreviations	Xiv
.....	
List of Figures	xvi
.....	
List of Table	xxiii
.....	
Chapter (1) Introduction	1
.....	
1.1 Renewable Energy	2
.....	
1.2 Rise of Nanophotonic	5
.....	
1.3 Why Thin Solar Cells?	5
.....	
1.3.1-Reduced Cost	6
.....	
1.3.2-Flexibility	6
.....	
1.4 Importance of Silicon	7
.....	
1.5 Thesis objective	7
.....	
1.6 Summary	7
.....	

Chapter 2 Basic Physics of Solar Cells	9
.....	
2.1 Introduction	9
.....	
2.1.1 Solar Irradiance	10
.....	
2.1.2 Atmosphere	11
.....	
2.1.3 Air mass 1.5G reference spectrum	11
.....	
2.1.4 Semiconductors	11
.....	
2.1.5 Bandgap	12
.....	
2.1.6 Intrinsic carriers	13
.....	
2.1.7 Doping	13
.....	
2.1.8 Equilibrium carrier concentrations	14
.....	
2.1.9 Light absorption	15
.....	
2.1.10 Absorption depth	16
.....	
2.1.11 Carrier movement	16
.....	
2.1.12 Diffusion	17
.....	
2.1.13 Drift	18
.....	
2.1.14 Recombination	18
.....	
2.1.15 Surface recombination	20
.....	
2.2 PN-junction	21
.....	
2.2.1 Dark behavior	23
.....	

2.2.2	Solar Cell behavior	23
2.2.3	Ideal solar cell equations	25
2.2.4	Shockley-Queasier limit or detailed balance	26
2.3	Loss mechanisms	27
2.3.1	Optical losses	27
2.3.2	Resistive losses	29
2.3.3	Recombination losses	30
2.4	Generations of Solar Cells	31
2.4.1	First Generation PV	32
2.4.1.1	Monocrystalline solar panels	32
1.4.1.1.a	Advantages	32
1.4.1.1.b	Disadvantages	33
2.4.1.2	Polycrystalline Silicon Solar Cells	33
1.4.1.2.a	Advantages	34
1.4.1.2.b	Disadvantages	34
2.4.2	Second Generation PV	34
2.4.2.1	Thin-Film Solar Cells (TFSC)	35
1.4.2.1.a	Advantages	36
1.4.2.1.b	Disadvantages	36
2.4.3	Third Generation	38

2.4.3.1	Dye-Sensitized Solar Cell Technology	38
1.4.3.2	Perovskite solar cells	39
2.5 Light trapping in solar cell		40
2.5.1	Nanowire Solar Cell	42
2.5.2	Plasmonic Solar Cell	43
2.5.3	Surface Texturing Solar Cell	45
2.6 Summary		46
Chapter 3: Computational techniques		48
3.1	Why computational modeling?	48
3.2	Overview of numerical methods for highly efficient nanostructured Solar Cells	50
3.3	Advantages of FDTD method	50
3.4	Overview of FDTD method	51
3.5	Frequency - dependent materials in FDTD Method	55
3.6	Boundary conditions	57
3.6.1	Periodic boundary conditions (PBCs)	58
3.6.2	Perfectly matched layers (PML)	59
3.7	Lumerical FDTD solutions	60
3.8	How to avoid the divergence in FDTD simulation?	61
3.8.1	Dt stability	61
3.8.2	PML considerations	61

3.9 The electrical Simulator	62
.....	
3.10 Summary	64
.....	
Chapter 4: Highly Efficient Nanopyramid Solar Cell	66
.....	
4.1 Introduction	66
.....	
4.2 Optical and electrical simulation strategy	69
.....	
4.3 Results and discussion	72
.....	
4.3.1 Optical analysis	72
.....	
4.3.2 Electrical analysis	83
.....	
4.3 Summary	89
.....	
Chapter 5: Conclusions and future work	91
.....	
5.1 Conclusions	91
.....	
5.2 Future work	92
.....	
References	94
.....	

Acknowledgments

I would like to thank all professors and colleagues who supported me to the research work presented in this thesis.

I would like to dedicate this thesis to the soul of Dr. Hala Hosny. I am indebted to Dr. Hala Hosny, Associate Professor at the department of Physics, Faculty of Science, Ain Shams University, for her encouragement, advice and guidance throughout this envelopment and in the completion of this work. Deep appreciation is owed to her for providing me interesting ideas, sharing her knowledge and aiding me through writing theses.

I would like to thank Dr. Mohammed Farahat, Associate Professor at Nanotechnology Engineering Program, University of Science and Technology, Zewail City of Science and Technology and ASSOC Professor at Mathematics and Engineering Physics Department, Faculty of Engineering, Mansoura University for suggesting a novel and excellent point of research along with his continuous encouragement, valuable and abundant discussions throughout this work. His careful reading of the manuscript is greatly acknowledged.

My deepest gratitude goes to Dr. Hassan Ramdan and Dr. Mohammed Hassan both from Basic Science department at faculty of Computer and Information Sciences, Ain Shams University for their most enlightening support and encouragement.

This dissertation was accomplished with the help and support of several collaborators. I would like to express my deep gratitude to Dr. Mohamed Hussien, Assistant Professor of photonics at Zewail City of Science and Technology as well as at Department of Physics, Faculty of Science, Ain Shams University, for his continuous and invaluable guidance. His professional capabilities and the endless support that he has given me through my study will always be recalled and appreciated. He was always willing to answer and discuss any questions.

I am very fortunate to have been able to work with a number of very dedicated and talented research colleagues at photonics in Zewail City of Science and Technology. I would like to thank Dr. Shima Ali for collaborations through training in clean room.

I would like to specially thank Prof. Salah Obayya the Director of the Center for Photonics and Smart Materials (CPSM) at Zewail City in being an inspiration for me to take up the field of photonics not only as a field of research but also as a career. I appreciate all his contributions of time, ideas, and getting fund to make all research work from CPSM are experience stimulating and productive.

I would like to specially thank Prof. Ahmed Zewail for the opportunity to contribute to the Egypt National project: Zewail City of Science and Technology.

I thank the CPSM researchers for effective suggestions and discussions.

I would like to dedicate my work to my beloved mother and sister as well as my uncle. None of my achievements would not have been possible without their absolute love and support.

Abstract

In this thesis, the optical and electrical characteristics of modified nanopyramid grating silicon solar cells (SCs) are numerically reported and analyzed. The modified grating SC consists of an upper tapered nanopyramid and a lower nanorectangular part. The geometrical parameters of the proposed design are tuned to maximize the optical absorption and hence the ultimate efficiency. The finite-difference time-domain and finite-element methods are utilized via Lumerical software packages for studying the optoelectronics performance of the suggested design. In this investigation, short-circuit current density (J_{sc}), optical generation rate, open-circuit voltage (V_{oc}), electrical fill factor, and electrical power conversion efficiency (PCE) are calculated thoroughly. Moreover, the effects of the doping concentration and carrier lifetime on the device performance are investigated. The modified design provides an optical ultimate efficiency of 40.93% and optical J_{sc} of 33.49 mA/cm², respectively, with an improvement of 28.3% over the conventional nanopyramid SC. This enhancement is due to the ability of the grating sidewalls to trap more light through the active layer. Additionally, the spacing between the adjacent nanopyramid structures exhibit microcavity resonance, which contributes to light broadband absorption enrichment. The p-i-n axial doping of the proposed SC exhibits V_{oc} of 0.57 V, J_{sc} of 28.42 mA/cm², and PCE of 13.3%, which are better than the V_{oc} of 0.559 V, J_{sc} of 19.6 mA/cm², and PCE of 8.95% of a conventional nanopyramid SC.

In this thesis, Chapter 1 gives a brief introduction for energy world consumption

Chapter 2 introduces an overview of the physics principles of solar cells. Optical and electrical characteristics of solar cells are represented. Solar cell generations and their efficiency are examined. Moreover, Light trapping techniques in silicon nanostructured solar cells are reported.

Chapter 3 describes simulation and analysis of solar cell structures. The formulation of the FDTD and the electrical simulator are discussed. The advantages of the numerical method are considered. In addition, a literature review about nanostructured solar cell is represented.

Chapter 4 discusses an overview of the major common numerical modeling techniques used in studying the proposal design. The optical properties of the proposed silicon nanostructured design solar cell are discussed and analyzed. Also, the electrical characteristics of the suggested design are presented.

Chapter 5 shows the conclusion of the presented research work and the future work linked to the topic of this thesis.

Key Words:

Nanopyramids, FDTD, Solar Cells, Thin Film

List of Publications

Journal Papers

- 1- Amr Hisham K. Mahmoud, Mohamed Hussein, Mohamed Farhat O. Hameed, M. Abdel-Aziz, H. M. Hosny, and S. S. A. Obayya, "Optoelectronic performance of a modified nanopyramid solar cell," *J. Opt. Soc. Am. B* 36, 357-365 (2019)

List of Symbols

G_p	The optical generation rates of holes
\vec{J}_n	The current densities of electrons
\vec{J}_p	The current densities of holes
G_n	The optical generation rates of electrons
N_A	The net ionized dopant density for acceptors
N_D	The net ionized dopant density for donors
n_1	Index of refraction of the incident medium
n_2	Index of refraction of the refractive medium
$C_{n, \text{ Auger}}$	Auger recombination of electrons for Silicon at 300K
$C_{p, \text{ Auger}}$	Auger recombination of holes for Silicon at 300K
$C_{\text{radiative}}$	Radiative recombination coefficient for Silicon at 300K
θ_1	Angle of incidence
θ_2	Angle of refraction
$\frac{\partial n}{\partial y}$	Electron Concentration Gradient
$\frac{\partial p}{\partial y}$	Hole Concentration Gradient
τ_n	Electron SRH recombination lifetime
τ_p	Hole SRH recombination lifetime
c	Speed of Light
D_n	Diffusivity of Electrons
D_p	Diffusivity of Holes
E	electric field
E_g	Gap Energy
E_{ph}	Energy Photons
ϵ_{r1}	The real part of dielectric material
ϵ_{r2}	The imaginary part of dielectric material
f	Frequency
FF	Fill factor
G	Generation Rate of Carriers
h	Planck's Constant
J_0	Dark saturation current density
J_{dark}	Dark current density
$J_{\text{generation}}$	Thermal generation current density
J_L	Light generated current density

J_m	Maximum current density
$J_{recombination}$	Recombination current density
J_{sc}	Short circuit current density
k	Extinction Coefficient
k_b	Boltzmann Constant
l	Mean Free Path Between Collisions
L_n	Length a minority electron
L_p	Length a minority hole
n	Ideality factor
N	The total number of atoms per unit volume
η	Efficiency
n_0	Free Electron Concentration
N_0	Photon Flux at The Surface
p_0	Free Hole Concentration.
P_{in}	Photons which reached by the sun in established solar cell
P_m	Maximum power
SRV	surface recombination velocity
T	Temperature
t	Average Time Between Collisions
T	Temperature
V	Applied voltage on solar cell
$V_{avg,n}$	Electron Drift Velocity
$V_{avg,p}$	Hole Drift Velocity
V_m	Maximum voltage
V_{oc}	Open circuit voltage
x	Distance from The Surface
α	Absorption Coefficient
γ	Rate of dumping
ϵ_0	Dielectric electric constant coefficient
λ	Wavelength
μ_n	electron mobility
μ_p	hole mobility
τ_{Aug}	Average recombination times for Auger recombination
τ_n	Electron minority carrier lifetime
τ_p	Hole minority carrier lifetime
$\tau_{radiative}$	average recombination times for radiative recombination
τ_{SRH}	Average recombination times for SRH recombination
χ	Electric susceptibility
$A(\vec{r},\lambda)$	Optical absorption
$g(\vec{r},\lambda)$	Optical generation rate
m_0	The electron mass
ω_0	Resonant frequency

List of Abbreviations

A	Lattice constant
ABCs	Absorbing boundary conditions
AM 1.5D	Air Mass Direct Earth
AM 1.5G	Air Mass Global Earth
AM0	Air Mass Zero
ARC	Antireflection coating
a-Si	Amorphous silicon
BCs	The boundary conditions
B _p	Pyramid base
CdTe	Cadmium telluride
CIS/CIGS	Copper indium gallium selenide
c-Si	Monocrystalline silicon
FDTD	Finite difference time domain
FEA	Finite element analysis
F _s (λ)	The photon flux density
GaAs	Gallium arsenide
Ge	Germanium
GTD	The geometrical theory of diffraction
h _p	Pyramid height
h _r	Rectangle height
LSPR	Localized surface plasmon resonance
MOM	The method of moment
NCs	Nanocones
NHs	Periodic nanohole
NWs	Nanowires
P	Periodicity
PCE	Power conversion efficiency
PERL	Passivated emitter rear locally diffused
PML	The perfect matched layer
PV	Photovoltaic
RCWA	Rigorous coupled wave analysis
R _s	Series resistance
R _{sh}	Shunt resistance
Si	Silicon
SiNW SC	Single nanowire solar cell
SPPs	Surface plasmon polaritons

SQ	Shockley-queasier
SRH	Shockley-read-hall
T	Substrate thickness
TCO	Transparent conductor oxide
TE	The transverse electric
TFPV	Thin-film photovoltaic cells
TiO ₂	Titanium dioxide
TM	The transverse magnetic
UV	Ultraviolet
W _r	Rectangle width
λ _f	Wavelength striking the solar cell

List of Figures

Fig 1.1: World total primary energy supply from 1971 to 2030[5], [6].	1
Fig 1.2: Renewable energy sources vector infographics: solar, wind, energy storage, heat pump, geothermal power, bio energy and hydropower [14].	3
Fig 1.3: best cell efficiency in percentage ranged from 1975 to 2020 [15].	4
Fig2.1: schematic diagram of pn junction doped solar cell	9
Fig.2.2: Solar spectrum at various positions. The blue line is outside Earth’s atmosphere and is the reference spectrum (AM0). The green line is the direct sunlight light hitting a sun-tilted surface at 37o on the Earth’s surface (AM 1.5D). The red line is light hitting a sun-tilted surface at 37o including diffuse light and is the reference spectrum (AM 1.5G). The AM 1.5G spectrum is the most used reference spectrum [49], [50].	10
Fig.2.3: shows different semiconductors with different band gap energy [53].	12

Fig.2.4: shows Semiconductor bandgap for intrinsic, n doped and p doped.	13
Fig.2.5: represent the three possibility of photon interaction with solar cell semiconductor.	15
Fig.2.6: a. free carrier movement. b. Diffusion. A high concentration at $t = 0$ will be dispersed at some later time $t = t_{later}$ through random free carrier movement. c. Drift. After each scattering event the movement will be governed by the momentum and the force on the particle by the electric field.	17
Fig.2.7: a. radiative recombination b. SRH recombination c. auger recombination.	19
Fig.2.8: a. The n-doped (p-doped) region has an excess of electrons (holes) but are neutrally charged b. Electrons (holes) diffuse against their concentration gradient and leave behind two charged regions c. The charged ions create an electric field which exerts a force on the electrons (holes), that in equilibrium is balanced with the diffusion “force” d. The bands are bend in order to have a constant Fermi level across the junction.	22
Fig2.9: Solar Cell behavior 1) electron hole pair created as a product of photon striking solar cell 2) carriers generated by space charge region separated by electric field.	24

Fig2.10: a. Idealized JV-curves solar cell under irradiated and dark environments. The illuminated curve is principally the dark curve shifted down by the $JL=J_{sc}$. The maximum power P_m that can be obtained is the area of the biggest box that can fit inside the irradiated JV-curve. fill factor FF Is the difference between $J_{sc}V_{oc}$ and J_mV_m is the fill factor FF, reverse bias is the negative voltage. While the positive voltage is called forward bias. b. Measurement of maximum efficiency single nanowire solar cell (SiNW SC) from [81].

..... 25

Fig2.11: a. The three main optical loses in solar cells. 1) Photons being reflected by surface solar cell or absorbed in the top contact. 2) Photons being reflected on the top front surface. 3) Photons passing through the whole solar cell without being absorbed.

b. Solar cell with ARC and surface texturing 1- light strike the top surface with an angle below $\theta_i = \sin^{-1}(n_{solar}n_{air})$. 2- light strike the solar cell with an angle higher than θ_i will be reflected backward by solar cell. 3-the average path length for photons inside solar cell $4n^2$ solar thickness.

..... 29

Fig2.12: PN junction solar cell device schematic. In parallel with the solar energy converter is the normal diode which create the dark current. The shunt resistance R_{sh} is also parallel to the solar converter, and the series resistance R_s is series connected.

..... 30

Fig2.13: schematic diagram of silicon crystal structure of **a.** monocrystalline silicon **b.** polycrystalline silicon **c.** amorphous silicon

..... 31

Fig2.14: classification of PV solar cell.

..... 37

Fig2.15: schematic diagram on how Dye-sensitized solar cells work Light transmitted by the transparent electrode of a dye-sensitized solar cell is absorbed by a dye (red), which cover titanium dioxide (TiO₂) nanoparticles (gray). The process forms electron-hole pairs (e⁻/h⁺). Electrons travel through the TiO₂ layer to one electrode as holes travel through an electrolyte (blue) to the other electrode, generating electric current [113], [114].

..... 38

Fig2.16: Perovskite solar cells: How they work Light passing through the transparent electrode (green) of a perovskite solar cell onto a layer of a photosensitive perovskite material (blue) stimulates excitations called electron-hole pairs (e⁻/h⁺). The charged particles separate and diffuse through the charge-conducting layers to their respective electrodes, there by generating electric current.

..... 39

Fig2.17: shows that the sun's rays are drawn into a nanowire, which stands on a substrate. At a given wavelength the sunlight is concentrated up to 15 times. Consequently, there is great potential in using nanowires in the development of future solar cells.

..... 42

Figure 2.18: Plasmonic light-trapping for thin-film solar cells. (a) Metal nanoparticles on the top surface of the solar cell. (b) Metal nanoparticles implanted in the semiconductor solar cell. (c) Metal nanoparticles or periodic arrays at the metal/semiconductor solar cell interface [136].

..... 43

Fig2.19: Simple light trapping. (A) The active region of a solar cell as an optically homogeneous slab of refractive index n where no light trapping utilized. (B) Planar bottom mirror. (C) Random surface texture with a planar bottom mirror. (D) Inverted pyramids with planar bottom mirror [139].	45
Fig.3.1: Yee cell utilized by a FDTD algorithm [149].	53
Fig.3.2: upper view of Si nanowire with (a) square lattice (b) triangular lattice (c) hexagonal lattice. Spotted squares signify unit cells of each geometric structure with periodic boundary conditions.	59
Fig.3.3: Simulation strategy of nanostructured solar cell.	62
Fig.4.1: (a) 3D representation of conventional nanopyramid SC [173] and (b) The short circuit current as a function of the filling factor FF [173].	69
Fig.4.2: schematic diagram of the modified pyramid SC (a) 2D unit cell and (b) 3D representation	70
Fig.4.3: (a) Absorption spectra, (b) η and J_{sc} of planner, conventional nanopyramid SC, and modified nanopyramid SC. Electric field profiles are shown through the (c) planer, (d) conventional nanopyramid and (e) modified nanopyramid SC at $\lambda = 943\text{nm}$, respectively.	74

Fig.4.4: Electric field profiles of (a), (d) nanorectangle, (b), (e) nanopyramid and (c), (f) modified nanopyramid at $\lambda = 500\text{nm}$ and $\lambda = 977\text{nm}$.	76
.....	
Fig.4.5: The propagation direction and strength of transmission diffraction orders of the (a) modified nanopyramid and (b) conventional nanopyramid at $\lambda = 943 \text{ nm}$, and (c) number of diffraction orders verses wavelength.	77
.....	
Fig.4.6: (a) Variation of the ultimate efficiency with the rectangle height h_r , (b) wavelength dependent absorption at different rectangle heights and steady state electric field profiles at $\lambda = 700 \text{ nm}$ for the modified nanopyramid at rectangle height of (c) $h_r=100 \text{ nm}$ and (d) $h_r=800 \text{ nm}$.	79
.....	
Fig.4.7: (a) Variation of the ultimate efficiency with the rectangle width W_r , (b) wavelength dependent absorption at different rectangle widths. The steady state electric field profiles at $\lambda= 700 \text{ nm}$ for the modified nanopyramid at (c) $W_r=980 \text{ nm}$ and (d) $W_r=1200 \text{ nm}$.	80
.....	
Fig.4.8: (a) Variation of the ultimate efficiency with the nanopyramid base B_p , (b) wavelength dependent absorption at different nanopyramid bases and steady state electric field profiles at $\lambda= 700 \text{ nm}$ for the modified nanopyramid at nanopyramid base of (c) $B_p=700 \text{ nm}$ and (d) $B_p=400 \text{ nm}$.	82
.....	
Fig.4.9: Schematic diagram of a unit cell of the (a) modified nanopyramid design (b) conventional nanopyramid SC.	83
.....	

Fig.4.10: (a) JV curve and (b) PV curve of nanopyramid and modified nanopyramid designs. The generation field profiles of the nanopyramid and the modified nanopyramid are shown in Fig. 8 (b) and (c), respectively at $\lambda= 700$ nm.

..... **85**

Fig.4.11: (a) JV curve and (b) PV curve at different surface recombination velocities

..... **86**

Fig.4.12: Variation of the open circuit voltage (V_{oc}) and short circuit current density (J_{sc}) with N doping concentration (a) N layer thickness 300 nm (b) N layer thickness 2100 nm, (c) PCE of the modified nanopyramid at N layer thickness 300 nm and 2100 nm and (d) variation of the short circuit current density (J_{sc}) with the N layer thickness.

..... **88**

Fig.4.13: A flow chart of the fabrication process of the reported design.

..... **89**

List of Table

Table 4.1: The initial geometrical parameters of the conventional nanopyramid [160], [173] and modified nanopyramid designs **74**

Table 4.2: The geometrical parameters of the conventional nanopyramid [160], [173] and modified nanopyramid designs **82**

Table 4.3: The electrical parameters of the modified nanopyramid unit cell [162]. **84**

Table 4.4: Electrical results of conventional nanopyramid and the modified nanopyramid SCs. **85**

Chapter (1)
Introduction

Chapter (1) Introduction

During the last few decades, the consideration towards sustainability has constantly enhanced. The present fossil-fuel based economy has recognized to be no longer maintainable, because of political, economic, and environmental concerns. The global need of energy has more than doubled through the last 40 years as shown in Fig1.1, and the estimates indicate a demanded growth of 50% with respect to the current situation [1]. This advance raise in global consumption can be mostly ascribed to growing countries, with countries like China and India and the Middle East region participating in a major role among them [2]. The frequently growing energy command cannot be fulfilled by presently - utilized non-renewable energy sources, mostly fossil fuels (i.e. oil, coal, natural gas etc.), which at the current utilization rate will encounter a (relatively) rapid depletion. Moreover, the resources of oil and gas are focused in a small number of countries, which can product in instability of the energy costs (furthermore to the possible price increase produced by the resources depletion); this unpredictability could pose a threat to the worldwide energy provide security [3], [4].

Fig 1.1: World total primary energy supply from 1971 to 2030[5], [6] .

1.1 RENEWABLE ENERGY

Renewable energy is energy generated from sources that do not run down or can be reinstated within a life time [7]–[9]. The most regular examples involve solar, wind, geothermal, biomass, hydropower and wind power as shown in Fig1.2 [7]. This is differed to non-renewable sources for instance fossil fuels.

Most renewable energy is obtained directly or indirectly from the sun. Sunlight can be captured directly utilizing solar technologies. The sun's heat drives winds, whose energy is taken with turbines. Plants also depend on the sun to produce and their stored energy can be used for bioenergy [10], [11]. Not all renewable energy sources depend on the sun. Such as, geothermal energy uses the Earth's internal heat, tidal energy depends on the gravitational pull force of the moon, and hydropower relies on the stream of water. Renewable energy accounts for 13.5% of the world's total energy resource, and 22% of the world's electricity [12]. Renewable energy systems are a main topic when considering the globe's energy upcoming for two major reasons:

1-Renewable energy systems generate energy from sources that will not deplete.

2-Renewable energy systems make less greenhouse gas emissions than fossil fuel energy systems.

Although renewable energy systems are more suitable for the environment and generate fewer emissions than conventional energy sources, several of these resources still face problems in being deployed at a large scale including, but not restricted to, high start-up capital costs, technological barriers, and intermittency challenges [7], [9], [13].

Solar energy is the cleanest renewable energy source available. Modern technology can employ this energy for numerous uses, which include

generating electricity, causing no pollution, and Reducing dependence on oil and fossil fuels.

Fig 1.2: Renewable energy sources vector infographics: solar, wind, energy storage, heat pump, geothermal power, bio energy and hydropower [14].

For the next few decades, solar panels have steadily decreased in cost per watt and increased in power conversion efficiency. Figure 1.3 shows the record of the highest efficiency research solar cells over the past few decades. The development of solar cells has branched out into different technologies, ranging from the crystalline semiconductor solar cells (such as silicon, gallium arsenic, and multijunction variants) to second generation thin-film solar cells and emerging third generation solar cells (dye-sensitized, perovskite, organic and quantum-dot solar cells). The emerging photovoltaic (PV) have a relatively low efficiency. However, their cost is low and they have a promising potential for higher efficiency, putting them on par with conventional solar cells.

Fig 1.3: best cell efficiency in percentage ranged from 1975 to 2020 [15].

1.2 Rise of Nanophotonic

In parallel with the improving and developing of photovoltaic technology over recent years, advance of the field of nanophotonic is growing. The extraordinary ability to study and manipulate light on a nanoscale has been encouraged by recent advances in technology such as near field optics, electron beam lithography, as well as more advanced.

Computation techniques such as finite element analysis (FEA) [16], [17], finite difference time domain (FDTD) [18], [19] and rigorous coupled wave analysis (RCWA) [20], [21] have been developed to study solar cell devices. On the other hand, Fields such as those based on plasmonics [22], [23], photonic crystals [18], [24] and metamaterials [25], [26] have been arose, motivating the enlargement of knowledge associated with nanoscale light operation. This has led to remarkable strides in the improvement of fields such as nano scale lasers [27], quantum optics [28], [29], near field imaging [30]–[32] and others. In spite of the continual growth of the closely linked fields of photovoltaics and nanophotonics, only recently have they begun to merge, giving birth to an interesting and rich new research frontier, that of nanophotonic solar cells [33]–[35].

1.3 Why Thin Film Solar Cells?

In spite of the best silicon (Si) solar cells existing many tens of microns thick, the supreme solar cell is one that is as thin as achievable [36]–[38]. There are many benefits for thinning the solar cell active layer, with the evident difficulty that it reduces light absorption probability. Film thickness differs from a few nanometers to tens of micrometers, this lets thin film cells to be more flexible, and lesser in weight. It is used in industry for building integrated photovoltaics, semi-transparent and photovoltaic glazing material that can be coated onto windows.

1.3.1-Reduced Cost

The best observable benefit of a thin solar cell is that it reduces the amount of raw material required to build the device. As of 2012, around 60% of a Si module cost is because of the Si alone [39], [40]. Decreasing the thickness of a Si device by an order of magnitude or more could considerably lower this cost. If the solar cell is made from an epitaxial material like an III-V, lessening the solar cell active layer thickness will lower both the amount of precursor gas needed for expansion as well as reactor run time for each device. Even though direct bandgap materials as gallium arsenide (GaAs) are already about thin ($\approx 2\text{-}5$ microns) compared to Si, their thickness could still in theory be reduced to less a micron.

1.3.2-Flexibility

As a crystalline wafer of a semiconductor for example, Si or GaAs is enormously inelastic and can destroy or shatter if handled inappropriately, a thin film of these materials can be tremendously flexible. This unlocks many latest applications for solar power that otherwise would not be achievable with wafer-based devices [39], [41], [42]. For instance, a flexible module could be rolled out and used when required as portable charging station, and rolled back up and stored suitably when not required. A flexible device could be merged into baggage or clothing, wrapped around curved surfaces, or even integrated into the outside of an automobile or aircraft. In addition, the flexibility of the solar cells could let them to fit into the small shape factor of wearable technology such as smartwatches, glasses, mobile phones and media players. Moreover, Flexible thin-film solar modules enhance the number of surfaces that can be utilized to improve solar energy generation, increase more opportunities for renewable, clean energy, supporting move the bar forward to a carbon-neutral future.

1.4 Importance of Silicon

Si are the most efficient semiconductor materials for solar cells. In addition, Si is the most abundant semiconductor material on earth. Although C-Si is of the first generation but it's over performance comparing with other semiconductors makes Si the best.

1.5 Thesis objective

The ultimate goal of this thesis is developing or improving new structures of silicon nanostructure solar cell with high efficiency. In this research work, a modified nanopyramid structure is studied and analyzed for solar cell applications. The suggested design consists of upper nanopyramid and bottom nanorectangle units. The geometrical parameters have been optimized by using 3D (FDTD) method to achieve broadband absorption through the reported design and maximize its ultimate efficiency, while electric parameters were optimized to improve power conversion efficiency. The analyzed parameters are absorption spectra, ultimate efficiency, short circuit current density, and open circuit voltage, fill factor and power conversion efficiency.

1.6 Summary

In this chapter, the importance of renewable energy has been reviewed. Solar energy plays an important role in our daily life application and high technology industries is well discussed. It is necessary to focus on silicon thin films technology in the future due to its properties of reducing cost and flexibility.

Chapter (2)
Basic Physics of Solar
Cells

Chapter 2 Basic Physics of Solar Cells

2.1 Introduction

The solar cell is defined as the device which directly converts the energy in light into electrical energy through the process of photovoltaics. The promotion of solar cell technology starts with the 1839 research of French physicist Antoine-César Becquerel. Becquerel detected the photovoltaic effect [43], while experimenting with a solid electrode in an electrolyte solution when he observes a voltage develop when the light fell upon the electrode. The importance of solar panels is offering pollution-free power sources, improving grid security, causing less electricity loss and reducing the financial costs of electricity [44], [45].

The solar cell presented in Fig. 2.1 fundamentally works as follows: Part of the sun's emitted photons strike the solar cell. If the photon has sufficient energy, the electron will be free from the crystal bond. The PN junction splits electron from the hole left behind it. The moving carriers (holes and electrons) are responsible for the current in the circuit.

Fig2.1.: schematic diagram of pn junction doped solar cell

2.1.1 Solar Irradiance

The Sun, approximately, releases radiation similar to a black-body with a temperature 5777K [46], The surface of sun is explained and described by black body radiation law [46]–[48]

$$I(\lambda_{\max}, T) = \frac{2\pi c^2 h}{\lambda^5 (e^{\frac{hc}{\lambda k_b T}} - 1)} \quad (2.1)$$

Where k_b is the Boltzmann constant, h is Planck's constant, c is the speed of light, λ is the wavelength, and T is the temperature

The delivered energy photons are given by $E_{ph} = \frac{h}{c\lambda} = hf$

Where f is the frequency.

Fig.2.2; Solar spectrum at various positions. The blue line is outside Earth's atmosphere and is the reference spectrum (AM₀). The green line is the direct sunlight light hitting a sun-tilted surface at 37° on the Earth's surface (AM 1.5D). The red line is light hitting a sun-tilted surface at 37° including diffuse light and is the reference spectrum (AM 1.5G). The AM 1.5G spectrum is the most used reference spectrum [49], [50].

2.1.2 Atmosphere

The atmosphere's numerous elements absorb sunlight at some specific wavelengths, which denotes that the spectra arriving the ground has some great dips when associated to the non-filtered spectrum in space, as explored in the red and blue lines in Fig. 2.2. Furthermore, the photons suffer several atmosphere thicknesses dependent on where in the world the solar cell is positioned. Clouds, barometric pressure, pollution, moisture and dust also influence the number of photons striking a given solar cell [51].

2.1.3 Air mass 1.5G reference spectrum

It is impossible to test the solar cell in natural sunlight or compare it with other because the efficiency is affected by the position on Earth, time of year, time of day, weather and atmospheric conditions. Hence, standard spectra have been ruled [52]. Lamps with special filters produces spectra to fair the comparison between solar cells. The air mass 1.5 (AM 1.5G) standard spectrum is applied to simulate solar cell. It is significant that AM 1.5G is normalized to 1000W/m^2 .

2.1.4. Semiconductors

Semiconductor materials conduct current under certain temperatures and different doping. The material characteristics forms electronic properties. The major semiconductors used for solar cells are Si, germanium (Ge), which are group IV materials, compound III-V materials such as GaAs, and II-VI compound materials such as cadmium telluride (CdTe) [37], [38]. The most important parameters that differs the semiconductors are the size of the bandgap and whether the bandgap is direct or indirect as shown in Fig2.3 [53].

Fig.2.3: Different semiconductors with different band gap energy [53].

2.1.5 Bandgap

A material property of any semiconductor is that it includes an electronic bandgap as seen in Fig.2.3. Bandgap is well defined as the range of energy in solid where no electron can exist. The size of bandgap energy is the distance between valence band and conduction band, which is full occupied with electrons, and the conduction band, which is unoccupied but where electrons can be momentarily excited into. Another definition of bandgap it is the energy required to remove electron from outer shell. The Fermi level is stated as the energy level that has a 50% possibility of being filled in thermodynamic equilibrium. The phonon interaction is required for indirect bandgap semiconductor to excite or recombine an electron between valence band and conduction band [54], [55].

Fig.2.4: Semiconductor bandgap for intrinsic, n doped and p doped

2.1.6 Intrinsic carriers

A hole is created as a result of thermal excitation of electron from the valence band to the conduction band. The concentration of electrons which is equal to concentration of holes is called intrinsic carrier concentration (n_i). Intrinsic carriers are excited due to low bandgap energy of semiconductor or raising the semiconductor temperature [56], [57].

2.1.7 Doping

The number of intrinsic carriers is normally too small to make effectual devices. In order to rise the number of free carriers, in addition to design an electronic potential structure inside the devices, atoms that are not generally part of the crystal are inserted through the material processing. The semiconductor is then doped and the inserted atoms are called dopants. If you desire to have more free electrons (holes) in a section of the semiconductor, atoms with extra (fewer) electrons in the outer shells than the atom they exchange are added [42], [58]. Atoms with extra electrons are identified as donors and atoms with fewer electrons are named as acceptors. An area with extra donors (acceptors) is called n (p)-doped. The Fermi level in an n (p)-doped semiconductor area is moved towards the conduction (valence) band.

The donor (acceptor) concentration is called N_D (N_A). As soon as doping, the doped region will have a superior concentration of one carrier class. This carrier is termed the majority carrier, however the carrier with the minimum density is called the minority carrier [42], [59]. Doping combination in planar growth is a mature experimentally and theoretically understood process. This denotes that the semiconductors doping profile can be approximately controlled, which is really essential to solar cells [57], [58].

2.1.8 Equilibrium carrier concentrations

With no applied bias, the number of carriers is at equilibrium concentration, hence

$$n_0 * p_0 = n_i^2 \quad (2.2)$$

Where n_0 is the free electron concentration and p_0 is the free hole concentration. When semiconductors are doped, the doping concentration is usually several orders of magnitude higher than the intrinsic carrier concentration [60]–[62]. It follows that

for an **n-Type** semiconductor,

$$n_0 = N_D, p_0 = \frac{n_i^2}{n_0} \quad (2.3)$$

and similarly for a **P-Type** semiconductor,

$$p_0 = N_A, n_0 = \frac{n_i^2}{p_0} \quad (2.4)$$

where N_D is the donor concentration and N_A is the acceptor concentration. The two equations imply that the minority carrier concentration is reduced when the semiconductor is highly doped.

2.1.9 Light absorption

There are different energy, frequency and wavelength for the photons that emitted from the sun. The relationship between energy gap of semiconductor and sun photon energy gives three possible probabilities [34], [51].

1-If $E_{ph} < E_g$, it will pass through semiconductor and interact very weak with it.

2-If $E_{ph} = E_g$, electron will have enough energy to get released from semiconductor valence band and reach the conduction band. This is the most efficient possible probability for creating a solar cell.

3-If $E_{ph} > E_g$, electron will release from semiconductor valence band and move to conduction band; however, the excess energy causes quick thermalizes atoms to the edge of conduction band (which is not efficient).

Fig.2.5: The three possibility of photon interaction with solar cell semiconductor.

2.1.10 Absorption depth

Absorption in semiconductors is principally defined by absorption coefficient

$$\alpha = \frac{4\pi k}{\lambda} \quad (2.5)$$

, where k is the extinction coefficient and λ is the photons wavelength. Low wavelength photons have a superior probability at being absorbed in the top of the semiconductor rather than the high wavelength photons. Therefore, high wavelength photons travel further in the semiconductor before being absorbed. The absorption depth is inverse proportional with the absorption coefficient. In semiconductors is the length a number of identical photons have to travel before only 37% of the original light intensity is left or their number has dropped by $1/e$. When the photon is absorbed by a semiconductor, a creation of electron hole occurs and consequentially the generation rate of carriers can be written as

$$G = \alpha N_0 e^{-\alpha x} \quad (2.6)$$

, where N_0 is the photon flux at the surface, and x is the distance from the surface. The absorption coefficient differs from one type of semiconductor to the other. The most important factor, take into consideration whether the semiconductor is direct or indirect in its bandgap energy. There are other factors affecting the direct semiconductors; like phonon interaction for absorption and recombination [34], [63]. On the other hand, indirect bandgap semiconductors have much longer absorption depths, as well much longer lifetimes for excited carrier [63], [64].

2.1.11 Carrier movement

Free electrons, which are not incorporated to an electric field, are permitted to transfer in the semiconductor. The unbounded carriers move in a random fashion by moving straight until scattering of a lattice atom, as represented in Fig. 2.6.a. The free carrier movement in a semiconductor is described by the diffusivity [19]:

$$D = \frac{l^2}{2t} \quad (2.7)$$

where l is the mean free path between collisions, which is material dependent, and t is the average time between collisions, which is lower at high temperatures. The diffusivity is different for electrons and holes. Without any interference there will be zero net movement of carriers. There are two mechanisms that carriers can follow for net movement: Diffusion or Drift [51], [65].

Fig.2.6: a. free carrier movement. b. Diffusion. A high concentration at $t = 0$ will be dispersed at some later time $t = t_{later}$ through random free carrier movement. c. Drift. After each scattering event the movement will be governed by the momentum and the force on the particle by the electric field.

2.1.12 Diffusion

There is a carrier concentration gradient because of higher concentration of carriers in some region than other. On the other side, gradient carrier concentration movement which is defined by Fick's law [66]–[68] is opposite to normal random carrier movement.

$$J_{D,n} = -D_n \frac{\partial n}{\partial y} \quad (2.8)$$

$$J_{D,p} = -D_p \frac{\partial p}{\partial y} \quad (2.9)$$

D_n (D_p) is the diffusivity of electrons (holes). $\frac{\partial n}{\partial y}$ ($\frac{\partial p}{\partial y}$) is the electron/hole concentration gradient. Diffusion mechanically spread the carriers. It worth noting that the diffusivity occurs under no presence of electric field.

2.1.13 Drift

The production of electric field in pn-junction semiconductor effects on carrier's motion by an exerting force. The carrier's movement influenced by the electric field as shown in Fig2.6.c. Consequence, the carriers will be in motion because of electric field. The drift velocity is defined by velocity of the electrons (holes) [65].

$$V_{avg,n} = -\mu_n E \quad (2.10)$$

$$V_{avg,p} = \mu_p E \quad (2.11)$$

Where μ_n (μ_p) is the electron (hole) mobility and \mathbf{E} is the the electric field.

2.1.14 Recombination

If the the equilibrium concentration is lower than minority carrier concentration, recombination mechanism will return the concentration to equilibrium. There are three major categories of recombination mechanism in semiconductor: Radiative recombination [57], Shockley-Read-Hall (SRH) recombination [69], and Auger recombination [70], [71] as illustrate in Fig2.7 the three major categories could be limited or reduced in semiconductors through some techniques but it impossible to avoid it.

Radiative recombination, or band-to-band recombination is defined as the combination between electrons from conduction band with hole from valence

band that leads to emit photons. The photon holds excess energy which is equal to bandgap. These photons are not absorbed by solar cell and hence they are lost.

SRH recombination is recombination at crystal defects. When a crystal defect creates a trap energy state within the bandgap this state can be occupied by an electron. If there is created a hole in the valence band before the electron leaves the trap state, then the electron fills the hole. Since SRH recombination is dependent on crystal defects, it is a loss mechanism that can be limited by using a pure crystal. SRH is most likely to occur via energy states in the middle of the bandgap, since it requires involvement of both carrier types, and the rate of state filling is dependent on the energy distance from the band edges.

Fig.2.7: a. radiative recombination b. SRH recombination c. auger recombination

Auger recombination is defined as the transferee of energy released from electron hole recombination to electron in conduction band. In addition, the electron lost this energy in form of thermalization in conduction band. Auger recombination is the most significant in high carrier concentration or heavy doping or high solar concentration.

Three recombination processes defined through the minority carrier life time

$$\frac{1}{\tau} = \frac{1}{\tau_{auger}} + \frac{1}{\tau_{SRH}} + \frac{1}{\tau_{radiative}} \quad (2.12)$$

Where $\tau_{radiative}$, τ_{SRH} , and τ_{Aug} are the average recombination times for radiative, SRH, and Auger recombination. An important feature of the recombination, is that it defines the length a minority carrier can diffuse in a semiconductor:

$$L_n = \sqrt{D_n \tau_n} \quad (2.13)$$

$$L_p = \sqrt{D_p \tau_p} \quad (2.14)$$

Where τ_n (τ_p) is the electron (hole) minority carrier lifetime. In-direct bandgaps will have long minority carrier lifetimes, since phonons are involved in the recombination processes. The total recombination rate is dependent on the excess carrier concentration, which is the concentration of carriers in excess of the equilibrium concentration.

2.1.15 Surface recombination

Surface recombination is a category of SRH defect recombination. At the surface of the semiconductor, the crystal lattice is abruptly ended, which leaves a high number of dangling bonds and possibly also contamination from the environment. The dangling bonds and contaminants become recombination sites for carriers [72], [73]. Surface recombination can be very detrimental to solar cell performance. This is especially true for small solar cells that have a large surface to volume ratio, since there is a short distance from where the carriers are generated to the recombination sites at the surface. Nanowire solar cells suffer from this problem, and great care must therefore, be taken to reduce the surface recombination to obtain a high-quality solar cell [72], [73].

2.2 PN-junction

if the photons interact with semiconductor solar cell, an electron hole pair will generate. To avoid electrons from recombination, the carriers should be separated from each other. The wide used separation system in pn junction. PN junction is separation system composed of n type region and p type region, where the two types are in contact as shown Fig. 2.8. the p type and n type are different doping of same semiconductor material e.g homojunction or different semiconductor materials e.g heterojunction [74], [75]. Homojunction solar cell consist of three part (p doped part- n doped part- space charge region) as demonstrated in Fig. 2.8.a. There will be a diffuse carrier (holes from p type to n-type- electrons from n-type to p-type) as a result of density gradient across the junction. The motion of electrons (holes) leaves charged ions [75], [76]. The different charges of atoms create electric field from n-type to p-type in Fig.2.8.b. the electric field exert a force that causes no charge carriers can move across the junction. Because of doping the fermi level moves forward the conduction (valence) band in n type (p-type) [75], [76]. The fermi level is constant across the levels when p-type and n-type are joined bands.

Fig2.8: **a.** The n-doped (p-doped) region has an excess of electrons (holes) but are neutrally charged **b.** Electrons (holes) diffuse against their concentration gradient and leave behind two charged regions **c.** The charged ions create an electric field which exerts a force on the electrons (holes), that in equilibrium is balanced with the diffusion “force” **d.** Bands are bend in order to have a constant Fermi level across the junction.

2.2.1 Dark behavior

The current density in pn junction can be expressed as:

$$J_{dark} = J_{recombination} - J_{generation} = J_0 \left(\exp \left(\frac{qV}{nK_B T} \right) - 1 \right) \quad (2.15)$$

If thermal generation current density ($J_{generation} = J_0$) and is independent of V , then recombination current density $J_{recombination} = J_0 \left(\exp \left(\frac{qV}{nK_B T} \right) \right)$. Where, J_0 is the dark saturation

current density or leakage current density, q is the elementary charge, V is the voltage, k_b is Boltzmann constant, T is the temperature, and n is the ideality factor.

J_{dark} is defined as the current that passes where there is no illumination. J_0 is a sign of individual current at certain temperature. Thermal generation current $J_{generation}$, since it is produced by minority carriers generated in the doped region that drift across the junction [77].

2.2.2 Solar Cell behavior

The electron hole Pairs are generated as a result of illuminating pn-junction by photons as illustrated in Fig.2.9. The carriers are capable to diffuse to space charge region and separate by built in electric field of space charge region in condition of the carriers created inside space charge region. If else the minority carriers will recombine sooner than they can be grabbed. If the carriers achieve external load, they transfer energy qV , where V is applied voltage on solar cell [78], [79].

Fig2.9: Solar Cell behavior 1) electron hole pair created as a product of photon striking solar cell 2) carriers generated by space charge region separated by electric field.

The equation which represent the efficiency (η) is defined as the ratio between the power that strikes the solar cell to the power that the solar cell produces

$$\eta = \frac{P_{out}}{P_{in}} \quad (2.16)$$

P_{in} is the photons which reached by the sun in established solar cell, although solar cells are hit by photons which comes from man-made light sources. P_m is the maximum power [80] and can be written as

$$P_m = J_m * V_m = FF * J_{sc} * V_{oc} \quad (2.17)$$

where V_m and J_m are the maximum voltage and maximum current density voltage at the greatest point of power that can be reached, J_{sc} is the short circuit current density, which is the current passed when the solar cell terminals are connected, V_{oc} is the open circuit voltage, which is the voltage when the terminals are under infinite load or not connected, and FF is the fill factor, which is a feature quality factor that demonstrates how efficiently the generated power can be obtained and modifies between $J_m V_m$ and $J_{sc} V_{oc}$. A better understanding of the parts of P_m can be glowed if we look at an idealized J-V curve for a solar cell as shown in fig2.10.

Fig2.10: a. Idealized JV-curves solar cell under irradiated and dark environments. The illuminated curve is principally the dark curve shifted down by the $J_L=J_{sc}$. The maximum power P_m that can be obtained is the area of the biggest box that can fit inside the irradiated JV-curve. fill factor FF Is the difference between $J_{sc} V_{oc}$ and $J_m V_m$ is the fill factor FF, reverse bias is the negative voltage. While the positive voltage is called forward bias. **b.** Measurement of maximum efficiency single nanowire solar cell (SiNW SC) from [81].

2.2.3 Ideal solar cell equations

For ideal solar cell pn-junctions under illumination [82], [83], the current density is set by:

$$J=J_0 \left(\exp \left(\frac{qV}{nkT} \right) - 1 \right) - J_L \tag{2.18}$$

Where J_L is the current density generated under illumination. From Eqn.2.18 it can be realized that the current created by light has the opposite sign of the dark current, and that the current created by light is normally independent of the voltage. The open circuit voltage is observed at the voltage where the dark and light currents are equal. By setting Eqn (2.18) equal to zero and isolating V , the ideal open circuit voltage can be determined through:

$$V_{oc} = \frac{nk_B T}{q} \ln \left(\frac{J_L}{J_0} + 1 \right) \tag{2.19}$$

The V_{oc} is generally defined by J_0 and ideality factor, since the light generated current density J_L is mainly controlled by the voltage [82], [83]. Fill factor is a key parameter in evaluating performance. Although a high ideality factor would seem to offer a very high V_{oc} secondary effects will reduce this. The ideal fill factor [84]–[86] can be expressed by the empirical expression.

$$FF = \frac{V_{oc} - \ln(V_{oc} + 0.72)}{V_{oc} + 1} \quad (2.20)$$

Where $V_{oc} = (qV_{oc}/nk_B T)$ is the normalized open circuit voltage. It is significant to deduce that the ideal fill factor is enhanced at higher V_{oc} , which is for example is true for higher bandgap materials and when subjected to sunlight. Alternatively, the ideal fill factor decreases at high diode ideality factors n . The real fill factor is also bound to be reduced by both series and shunt resistances [87]–[89].

2.2.4 Shockley-Queasier limit or detailed balance

The detailed balance limit is the theoretical highest efficiency value established for solar cells; proposed by Shockley and Queasier [90], [91], commonly named as the Shockley-Queasier (SQ) limit. The limit is analyzed by using a few key expectations:

1. P_{in} is the solar spectrum, or possibly a reference spectrum.
2. The bandgap E_g
3. Perfect collection: Ideality all created carriers are collected.
4. Perfect absorption: Every photon with an energy: $E_{ph} > E_g$ is absorbed and generates exactly one electron-hole pair.
5. band-to-band radiative recombination.
6. Constant cell temperature condition.

2.3 Loss mechanisms

In the aim of approaching the ideal case, a number of loss mechanisms have to be considered, in order to design optimally solar cells. There are three principal loss sources namely

1. Optical losses; mainly related to photons not being absorbed in the solar cell [92].
2. Connection losses; due to electrical circuits in solar cells [93].
3. Recombination losses; carried by carriers which recombine before they are collected [51].

2.3.1 Optical losses

Optical losses take place when the photons energy is less than the band gaps of the solar material; and hence is not absorbed [94], [95].

There are three main types of optical losses; basically, due to

1. Photons striking the top metallic contact
2. Photons being reflected by the top solar cell surface
3. Photons passing through the solar cell without being absorbed

In order to extract the carriers from the solar cell, electrical contacts are created at both ends. The top electrical connection, occupies space at the front surface area of the solar cell, and any photon hitting this surface area will be reflected or absorbed by the electrical contact. The area of the top contact is fabricated as thin as possible, A thin top contact area, though, raises the series resistance. A supplementary semi-transparent top contact, shielding the whole surface, is utilized, to raise the series resistance. This additional loses, since it will only transmit around 90% of the light.

Concerning the second source of optical losses, as light passes from a medium of refractive index (n_1) to another medium of refractive index (n_2). Part of light

will be reflected depending on the incident angle and the wavelength. There are two methods to minimize this reflection, an antireflection coating (ARC) or surface texturing, where ARC is composed of a thin layer of material with refractive index $n_{arc} = \sqrt{n_{air}n_{solar}}$. If the coating thickness is $0.25\lambda_f$, all the light within the wavelength (λ_f) striking the solar cell will be transmitted into the solar cell.

Moreover, the ARC is not efficient at larger angles between light rays and the surface of the solar cell. The ARC is very sensitive to light wavelength and angles. With the purpose of absorbing all photons that enter the solar cell, the material requires to be thick enough to be capable of absorbing all photons, however there is a limit to the thickness of the solar cell due to material cost. On the other hand, to activate the pn junction solar cell, it needs to absorb all photons and generate carriers within the diffusion length without recombining before extracting the carriers. Hence, it is ideal to fabricate a pn junction solar cell that is physically thin but optically deep, which is obtained by utilizing light trapping [96], [97].

The simplest way to double the optical path length in the pn junction solar cell is adding a mirror at the back of the solar cell. The optical path length can be expressively improved as the light will multiply many times between the surface texture at the top front of the solar cell and the mirror at the bottom back of the solar cell without exiting the solar cell [97], [98].

Fig2.11: **a.** The three main optical losses in solar cells. 1) Photons being reflected by surface solar cell or absorbed in the top contact. 2) Photons being reflected on the top front surface. 3) Photons passing through the whole solar cell without being absorbed **b.** Solar cell with ARC and surface texturing 1- light strike the top surface with an angle below $\theta_i = \text{Sin}^{-1} \left(\frac{n_{solar}}{n_{air}} \right)$. 2- light strike the solar cell with an angle higher than θ_i will be reflected backward by solar cell. 3- the average path length for photons inside solar cell $4n^2_{solar}$ thickness.

A Lambertian reflector is a totally randomizing reflector and the $4n^2_{solar}$ optical path enrichment is called the Lambertian limit [94], [99], which is the limit when using ray-tracing to express the optical pathway. Perfect texturing is very costly to produce, but many industrial solar cells have simple texturing.

2.3.2 Resistive losses

After adding the solar cell into circuit, extra loss mechanisms are presented. A model a circuit solar cell schematic that is shown in Fig.2.12 there are two resistors [42], [87], [88] in the schematic

1. Series Resistance R_s , which is in series connection
2. Shunt Resistance R_{sh} , which is in parallel connection with the diodes

The resistances mainly influence or affect the fill factor. This effect is simple to realize through JV solar cell characterization behavior. When the R_s

increases, the slope of the “voltage” end of the curve near the V_{oc} will be shallower. This means a reduction in maximum power square. Even if the slope of the curve is significantly affected by R_s the absolute value of the V_{oc} is not influenced. A decreased R_{sh} will affect in a sharper slope at the “current” end of the curve. A small of R_{sh} can be triggered by a short circuit that avoid or circumvent the solar diode, which expressly for nanowire solar cells can be a real concern. Such a short circuit can be very difficult to obtain visually, but will be simple to mark in an electrical measurement, since the solar cell will perform more like a resistor than a diode [87], [88].

Fig2.12: PN junction solar cell device schematic. In parallel with the solar energy converter is the normal diode which create the dark current. The shunt resistance R_{sh} is also parallel to the solar converter, and the series resistance R_s is series connected.

2.3.3 Recombination losses

The recombination of carriers before they are extracted and utilized is a very significant loss procedure in solar cells. To avoid unfavorable recombination which effects on current generation, carriers should be generated within a diffusion length of the junctions, so the carriers can diffuse to the junction and be extracted. The carriers must be generated closer to the junction instead of

center junction. High energy photons are usually absorbed very rapidly, so they are more exposed to surface recombination, however low energy photons are more exposed to bulk and rear contact recombination [100].

the number of minority carriers at pn junction solar cell control recombination through the carrier speed. Hence, the forward dark current which leads to enhance the open circuit voltage is influenced by those parameters [65], [101].

1. Minority Carriers number at the edge of the solar junction and this can be reduced by maximize the doping concentration [57].
2. Diffusion Length of the active solar material. The diffusion length is very important factor on solar cell, where the short diffusion length indicate that minority carriers recombine very rapidly, on the other hand the high doping decrease diffusion length, therefore in manufacture there is a tradeoff between high doping and diffusion length [51].
3. Surface passivation is a method to protect the carriers from achieving the surface by a window layer at the top front surface. A window layer is a lattice matched, wide bandgap material, and it should be as narrow as possible in order to minimize absorption of photons [102].

2.4 Generations of Solar Cells

Fig2.13: schematic diagram of silicon crystal structure of **a.** monocrystalline silicon **b.** polycrystalline silicon **c.** amorphous silicon

2.4.1 First generation of PV

2.4.1.1 Monocrystalline solar panels

Monocrystalline solar cells are manufactured from silicon ingots, which are cylindrical in form. To optimize minor costs and performance of a single monocrystalline solar cell, four sides are extracting from the cylindrical ingots to create silicon wafers, which is what provides monocrystalline solar panels their characteristic look [103].

An excellent method to distinguish between monocrystalline and polycrystalline solar panels is that polycrystalline solar cells examine perfectly rectangular with no smooth-edged [103].

2.4.1.1.a. Advantages

- Monocrystalline solar panels have the maximum efficiency rates since they are manufactured out of the top -grade silicon. The efficiency rates of monocrystalline solar panels are usually 15-20%. Sun Power harvests the highest efficiency solar panels on current world market. Their E20 series support panel conversion efficiencies of up to 20.1%.
- Monocrystalline silicon solar panels are high-efficient. Since these solar panels generate the ultimate power outputs, they also need the minimum amount of space associated to any other types. Monocrystalline solar panels supply up to four times the quantity of electricity as thin-film solar panels.
- Monocrystalline solar panels exist the longest. Most solar panel manufacturers put nearly 25-year guarantee on their monocrystalline solar panels.
- Tend to achieve better than the rated polycrystalline solar panels at quiet -light conditions are the determining aspects for most applications.

2.4.1.1.b. Disadvantages

- Monocrystalline solar panels are the greatest overpriced. From a financial position, a solar panel that is manufactured of polycrystalline silicon can be a better choice for some owners.
- If the solar panel is partly shielded with shade, snow or dirt, the whole circuit can stop working. Consider getting micro-inverters in preference to central string inverters if you believe coverage will be a tricky. Micro-inverters will make effective that not the entire solar array is influenced by shielding issues with only one of the solar panels.
- The Czochralski process [104] is utilized to produce monocrystalline silicon . It develops in large cylindrical ingots. Four sides are extracted of the ingots to produce silicon wafers. An important amount of the original silicon results as waste.
- Monocrystalline solar panels handle to be extra efficient in warm weather. Performance suffers as temperature rise, but less so than polycrystalline solar panels. For major home owner temperature is not a concern.

2.4.1.2 Polycrystalline Silicon Solar Cells

The primary solar panels manufactured from polycrystalline silicon, which also is called polysilicon (p-Si) or multi-crystalline silicon (mc-Si), were presented to the market in 1981 [105], [106]. Dissimilarity, monocrystalline silicon based solar panels, polycrystalline solar panels do not need the Czochralski process where, raw silicon is melted and poured in a shape of square mold, which is frozen and cut into extremely square wafers [105], [106].

2.4.1.2.a Advantages

- The process utilized to make polycrystalline silicon is cost less and simpler. The quantity of waste silicon is fewer compared to monocrystalline [105].
- Polycrystalline solar panels tend to have considerably lesser heat tolerance than monocrystalline solar panels. This technically indicates that they attain slightly worse than monocrystalline solar panels in extreme temperatures. Heat can influence the performance of solar panels and shorten their lifetimes. On the other hand, this effect is minor, and most users do not need to take it into consideration [107].

2.4.1.2.b Disadvantages

- The polycrystalline solar panels efficiency is typically ranged between 13-16%. Owing to minor silicon purity, polycrystalline solar panels are not as efficient as monocrystalline solar panels [105].
- Lower space-efficiency. It is normally require to cover a superior surface to harvest the same electrical power as you would with a solar panel based on monocrystalline silicon. Nonetheless, this does not indicate each monocrystalline solar panel perform superior than those made of polycrystalline silicon [105].
- Thin-film and Monocrystalline solar panels attend to be extra aesthetically pleasing since they have an additional uniform look associated with the speckled blue polycrystalline silicon [105].

2.4.2 Second Generation of PV

Presently, first technologies dominate PV market [63], which have reached a quantity level that causes them to be in competitive economically with non-renewable electricity production. On the other hand, since the significant cost reduction that admitted photovoltaic to accomplish grid parity only occurred in recent times, alternative technologies for the production of solar cells have

been widely researched for many years, in order to decrease production charges and to improve the conversion efficiency, consequently making them even more economically attracting than first generation PV. These new technologies can be split in two major groups, depending on their structural characteristics and development phase: second generation and third generation technologies as shown in fig 2.14.

second generation technologies involve single-junction devices that target to decrease the material utilization, while keeping the efficiencies of first generation PV [108]. While the absorber layers of wafer-made of silicon solar cells includes several hundreds of micrometers of material, these second generation solar cells are based on very thin layers deposited on cheap substrates, e.g: glass, polymer, or metal [108]. As a concern, less semiconductor material is necessitated to fabricate a cell of the same area, hence production charges can be significantly reduced. However, such thin absorber layers need the employment of light-trapping techniques, with the purpose of absorb an abundant amount of light and consequently achieve superior conversion efficiencies.

The main types of thin-film single-junction solar cells that have been commercially expanded are: amorphous (a-Si) and micro-crystalline silicon ($\mu\text{c-Si}$), cadmium-telluride (CdTe), Copper-Indium-Selenide (CIS) solar cells [109].

2.4.2.1 Thin-Film Solar Cells (TFSC)

The scientific base of how thin-film solar cells are produced is by depositing one or several photovoltaic material thin layers onto a substrate. They are also well-known as thin-film photovoltaic cells (TFPV). The various types of thin-film solar cells can be classified by the photovoltaic material which is deposited onto the substrate:

- Amorphous silicon (a-Si)

- Organic photovoltaic cells
- Copper indium gallium selenide (CIS/CIGS)
- CdTe

Based on the technology, thin-film module prototypes have achieved efficiencies ranged between 7–13% and manufacture modules perform at about 9%. Upcoming module efficiencies are assumed to improve near to the about 10–16% [37].

The market for thin-film PV developed at a 60% yearly rate from 2002 to 2007 [37]. In 2011, near to 5% of U.S. photovoltaic module consignments to the residential sector were made of thin-film [37].

2.4.2.1.a Advantages

- The simple mass-production and the low-cost fabrication. This provides them to manufacture more than crystalline-based solar cells.
- Their homogenous appearance supplies them look extra attractive.
- Can be become flexible, which supports many novel potential applications.
- Extreme temperatures and shielding have rarer effect on solar panel performance.

2.4.2.1.b Disadvantages

- Thin-film solar panels are in normal not very beneficial for in major residential situations. They are inexpensive, but they also need a lot of space. SunPower`s monocrystalline solar panels harvest up to four times the quantity of electricity as thin-film solar panels for the same measure of space.
- Low efficiency also indicates that the budgets of PV-equipment (e.g. supply structures and cables) will rise.

- Thin-film solar panels tend to damage and degrade earlier than mono- and polycrystalline solar panels, which is why they normally come with a shorter guarantee.

CdTe: Cadmium-telluride thin-film solar cells can attain superior efficiencies than amorphous and micro-crystalline silicon devices, with a current note of 19.6% [42]. The mixture of effective performance with low production charges makes CdTe the highest economical thin-film presently available. The main disadvantages of this technology are associated with the absorber materials: accessibility of tellurium can become a difficulty, while cadmium has toxicity that may reduce its use [110].

CIS and CIGS: These kinds of cells, whose absorber layer is based on a mixture of copper, indium, selenium, and finally gallium, propose the maximum conversion efficiencies of all thin film PV technologies, achieving values as extreme as 20.8%. The chief goals for this technology are currently to rise the performance of industrial modules, which is still considerably lower (efficiency 15.7%), and to improve the production facility and decreases its cost [111].

Fig2.14: classification of PV solar cell.

2.4.3 Third Generation of PV

Third-generation photovoltaic cells are solar cells that are potentially capable to overcome the Shockley–Queisser limit of 31 to 41% [112] power efficiency for single bandgap solar cells for example:

- Copper zinc tin sulfide solar cell (CZTS).
- Dye-sensitized solar cell "Grätzel cell"
- Organic solar cell
- Perovskite solar cell
- Quantum dot solar cell

2.4.3.1. Dye-Sensitized Solar Cell Technology

Fig2.15: schematic diagram on how Dye-sensitized solar cells work Light transmitted by the transparent electrode of a dye-sensitized solar cell is absorbed by a dye (red), which cover titanium dioxide (TiO₂) nanoparticles (gray). The process forms electron-hole pairs (e⁻/h⁺). Electrons travel through the TiO₂ layer to one electrode as holes travel through an electrolyte (blue) to the other electrode, generating electric current [113], [114].

The electrochemical dye solar cell was invented in 1988 by Professor Graetzel [115]–[117] of Lausanne Polytechnique, in Switzerland. The "Graetzel" dye cell uses dye molecules adsorbed in nanocrystalline oxide semiconductors, such as TiO₂, to collect sunlight [113], [114], [118]. Dye cells employ relatively inexpensive materials such as glass, Titania powder, and carbon powder. Graetzel's cell is composed of a porous layer of titanium dioxide

nanoparticles, covered with a molecular dye that absorbs sunlight, like the chlorophyll does in green leaves as shown in Fig2.15. Third generation solar cells are the cutting edge of solar technology. These solar cells can exceed the theoretical solar conversion efficiency limit for a single energy threshold material. Current research is targeting conversion efficiencies of 30-60% while retaining low cost materials and manufacturing techniques [37]. Third generation contains a wide range of potential solar innovations including multijunction solar cells, polymer solar cells, nanocrystalline-nanowire cells, quantum dot solar cells and dye sensitized solar cells.

2.4.3.2 Perovskite solar cells

Fig2.16: Perovskite solar cells: How they work Light passing through the transparent electrode (green) of a perovskite solar cell onto a layer of a photosensitive perovskite material (blue) stimulates excitations called electron-hole pairs (e^-/h^+). The charged particles separate and diffuse through the charge-conducting layers to their respective electrodes, thereby generating electric current.

A perovskite solar cell is a sort of solar cell which involves a perovskite structured compound, most usually a hybrid organic-inorganic lead or tin halide-based material, as the light-harvesting active layer. Perovskite materials [119] like methylammonium lead halides and all-inorganic cesium lead halide, are economical produce and simple to manufacture.

Solar cell efficiencies of devices using these materials have increased from 3.8% in 2009 to 23.3% in late 2018 in single-junction architectures, and, in silicon-based tandem cells 27.3% exceeding the maximum efficiency accomplished in single-junction silicon solar cells. Perovskite solar cells are the rapidest-advancing solar technology to date [120]. With the potential of realizing even higher efficiencies and very low production costs, perovskite solar cells have become commercially attractive.

Metal halide perovskites have unique features that make them exciting for solar cell applications. The raw materials utilized, and the achievable fabrication methods (for example various printing techniques) are both low costs. Their high absorption coefficient allows ultrathin films of approximately 500 nm to absorb the almost visible solar spectrum. These features mixed result in the probability to create low cost, high efficiency, thin film, lightweight and flexible solar modules.

2.5 Light trapping in solar cell

Reflection from the front surface is one of the contributors to the optical losses that prevent the sunlight from entering solar cell. The sunlight which is not absorbed by active layer is then absorbed in non-active layer material in the solar cell such as back reflector or transparent conductor oxide (TCO) [121]. The main reason for conventional solar cell to have a thick active material is to sufficiently absorb most of the sunlight. Light trapping aims at improving light absorption by designing the solar cell in a way so that path length of light stays inside the active material as long as possible [122]. Nowadays, texturing the surface with a random pyramid has been introduced in wafer-based Si solar cell. The highest efficiency of 24.7% has been achieved with passivated emitter rear locally diffused (PERL) cell incorporated with inverted pyramid structure at the front surface of the cell. Randomly textured front surface by laser techniques has also shows a good optical absorption and has largely

produced recently. However, the typical sizes of textured surface for wafer based solar cell are several times the size of the wavelength of the light which is unsuitable for a thin cell which is typically in order of few microns. Therefore, in order to be applied at thinner solar cell, a new light trapping method has to be introduced in order to avoid optical loss due to poor light absorption in thin film solar cell. With an appropriate light trapping technique, thin film solar cell also able to make multiple passes through the cell, and thus maintain a high optical path length such as wafer based solar cell [123].

There are many light trapping techniques has been introduced in order to enhance absorption of active layer in thin film solar cell. Light trapping could be divided by two main group; using photonic structures or plasmonic structures. Photonic structures could diffract propagating light in the active layer while the later exploiting scattering effect and localized surface plasmon resonance (LSPR) [124] to trapped light and hence enhanced absorption in active layer. Several examples for photonic structure [125], and plasmonic structure [25], [126] textured in front or back surface of solar cell has been introduced. In this study, the enhancement of optical absorption via periodic nanohole (NHs) [127] textured in front surface of silicon for light trapping in thin film solar cell has been investigated . By texturing front surface [128], [129] of the active layer, two effects were predicted; 1) light may couple in diffraction order and may enhanced path length of light in active material and 2) antireflective effect by nanostructure of periodic NH. In order to avoid recombination at the grain boundaries, monocrystalline silicon (c-Si) was selected as an active layer. The thickness of 1 μm active layer has been chose in this study to evade the high price of c-Si. It should be noted that the study is limited to optical analysis of the silicon solar cell, therefore electronic properties or recombination effect in solar cell are not included in this thesis.

2.5.1 Nanowire Solar Cell

Nanowires are based up on a flat substrate of semiconductor materials, such as silicon and germanium [130]. Nanowires are very tiny wires [131]. They are composed of metals such as silver, gold or iron [132]. Nanometer is measured as spatial measurement that is about 10^{-9} meters which are mostly used in nanotechnologies for the manufacturing of nano machines. The small nanowire is produced by Nano particles with a diameter as tiny as nanometer. Because of some unique physical light absorption properties of nanowires, the limit of how much energy we can use from the sun's rays is higher than previous believed. These results explain the numerous potentials of development of nanowire-based solar cells, says PhD Peter Krogstrup on the surprising discovery that is described in the journal Nature Photonics [133].

The research groups have during recent years studied how to develop and improve the quality of the nanowire crystals, which is a cylindrical structure with a diameter of about 10,000 part of a human hair. The nanowires are predicted to have great potential in the development not only of solar cells, but also of future quantum computers and other electronic products [134].

Fig2.17: shows that the sun's rays are drawn into a nanowire, which stands on a substrate. At a given wavelength the sunlight is concentrated up to 15 times. Consequently, there is great potential in using nanowires in the development of future solar cells.

It turns out that the nanowires naturally concentrate the sun's rays into a very small area in the crystal by up to a factor 15. Because the diameter of a nanowire crystal is smaller than the wavelength of the light coming from the sun it can cause resonances in the intensity of light in and around nanowires [135]. Thus, the resonances can give a concentrated sunlight, where the energy is converted, which can be used to give a higher conversion efficiency of the sun's energy, says Peter Krostrup, who with this discovery contributes to that the research in solar cell technology based on nanowires get a real boost. Nanowires are applicable in improves display screens on electronics devices, increasing the density of memory chips, reducing the size of transistors used in integrated circuits.

2.5.2 Plasmonic Solar Cell

Figure 2.18: Plasmonic light-trapping for thin-film solar cells. (a) Metal nanoparticles on the top surface of the solar cell. (b) Metal nanoparticles implanted in the semiconductor solar cell. (c) Metal nanoparticles or periodic arrays at the metal/semiconductor solar cell interface [136].

Plasmonic light trapping via metallic elements is of particular interest for enhancing the efficiency of thin film solar cells. Interface between a metal and a dielectric/semiconductor can support surface plasmons, which are collective oscillations of conduction electrons in metals bound to light oscillations in both metal and dielectric. Surface plasmons can be excited in metallic nanoparticles, where it is localized and has limited spatial extent, or along a metal-dielectric interface called surface plasmon polaritons (SPP), where it can propagate and confine light at the interface. Using plasmonic elements not only can improve the solar cell efficiency by trapping or concentrating light at the absorber layer but it can also serve as a back contact or a cheap anti-reflective electrode in some configurations [137].

Plasmonic structures can be integrated with a solar cell in three ways [138]. First, a plasmonic structure can be placed on the top surface of a solar cell. If it is in the form of metallic nanoparticles, then it can enhance absorption in the absorber layer by scattering the sunlight into it and reducing the reflection (Fig.2.18). If it is in the form of a metallic mesh directly on the absorber layer, then it can serve both as a scatterer and an electrode. Second, plasmonic nanoparticles can be embedded inside the absorber (Fig.2.18.b). They behave as sub wavelength lenses and enhance light absorption by concentrating the light locally. Third, metallic nanoparticles or corrugated metal films can be placed at the back surface of a cell (Fig.2.18.c). In the case of a metallic film, SPPs are excited at the interface between the metal and the absorber, which enhance optical field concentration and also couple the incident light into the guided modes of the thin absorber. It can also serve as the back contact of the cell where charge carriers are efficiently collected due to a very short distance, they travel to reach the contact. These three configurations are discussed in more details in the next sections.

2.5.3 Surface Texturing Solar Cell

Surface texturing, either in combination with an anti-reflection coating or by itself, can also be used to minimize reflection. Any "roughening" of the surface reduces reflection by increasing the chances of reflected light bouncing back onto the surface, rather than out to the surrounding air.1.

Fig2.19: Simple light trapping. (A) The active region of a solar cell as an optically homogeneous slab of refractive index n where no light trapping utilized. (B) Planar bottom mirror. (C) Random surface texture with a planar bottom mirror. (D) Inverted pyramids with planar bottom mirror [139].

Surface texturing can be accomplished in a number of ways. A single crystalline substrate can be textured by etching along the faces of the crystal planes. The crystalline structure of silicon results in a surface made up of textures such as pyramids. A planar solar cell with no light trapping may have an optical path length of one device thickness, although a solar cell with beneficial light trapping may have an optical path length of 50 times, indicating that light rebounds back and forth within the cell several times.

Light trapping is normally achieved by varying the angle at which light travels in the solar cell by having it be incident on an angled surface. A textured surface will not only decrease reflection as previously illustrated but will also couple light indirectly into the silicon [95], [139], [140], therefore giving a longer optical path length than the physical device thickness. The angle at which light is refracted into the semiconductor material is, according to Snell's Law, as follows:

$$n_1 \sin \theta_1 = n_2 \sin \theta_2 \quad (2.21)$$

where θ_1 and θ_2 are the angles for the light incident on the interface relative to the normal plane of the interface within the mediums with refractive indices n_1 and n_2 respectively. θ_1 and θ_2 .

2.6 Summary

In this chapter, the solar cell fundamentals, generation and characterization were discussed. A survey on the semiconductor properties and p-n junction characteristics was represented. Some light trapping techniques were described. An outline of photovoltaic generations was also involved.

Chapter (3)
Computational techniques

Chapter 3: Computational techniques

This chapter deals and introduces the numerical techniques that can be used to design highly efficient nanostructured SCs. The main function of the numerical method is to calculate and optimize the performance of the intended solar cell designs; presently considered as computational photonics; to minimize the development and manufacture cost as well as the time required for producing new nanostructured different designs. Moreover, the numerical computational method supports the development of a new generation of photonic communication system components: e.g photonic integrated circuits, photonic biological sensors, photonic integrated circuits, etc. To optimize the optical characterization of the suggested nanostructure SCs, Lumerical finite difference time domain (FDTD) software packages is used [18]. The software is based on a FDTD method to solve Maxwell's equations in 3D. It is considered an efficient tool for investigating the interaction of UV, visible and IR radiation with the sub-wavelength periodic and complex structures. To study the electrical characterization of the proposed nanostructure design, we utilize Lumerical Device software package. The software is based on a finite element method to solve drift-diffusion equations and Poisson continuity equations in 3D.

3.1 Why computational modeling?

Simulation modeling explains real-world problems efficiently and safely. It provides an essential method of analysis which is easily verified and understood. Across industries, the simulation modeling provides effective solutions by providing clear insights into complex systems [141], [142].

Simulation supports experimentation on a valid digital illustration of a system. Unlike physical modeling, like making a scale copy of a building, simulation modeling is computer based and employs algorithms and equations.

Simulation software gives a dynamic environment for the investigation of computer models while they are including the chance to view them in 2D or 3D.

The computational modeling could help in the following cases:

- Virtual experiments with simulation models are less expensive and take less time than experiments with real assets. Marketing campaigns can be tested without alerting the competition or unnecessarily spending money.
- Simulation models can be animated in 2D/3D, allowing concepts and ideas to be more easily verified, communicated, and understood. Analysts and engineers gain trust in a model by seeing it in action and can clearly demonstrate findings to management.
- Simulation model can capture and gave many more details than an analytical model, providing increased accuracy and more precise forecasting. Mining companies can significantly cut costs by optimizing asset usage and knowing their future equipment needs.
- Simulation model is very fast and can accomplish many tasks simply. It can do very massive calculations in just a fraction of a second. Furthermore, it can store huge amount of data in it.
- Simulation modeling provides an easy method to test and explore various scenarios. The effect of changing staffing levels in a plant may be noted without putting production at risk.

Nowadays, simulation modeling takes place and contributes in Aerospace Engineering, Chemical/Process Engineering, Pure Sciences, Design and Analysis of Computer Experiments [143], [144].

3.2 Overview of numerical methods for highly efficient nanostructured Solar Cells

In the aim of introducing a design with large scale optical devices and circuits, it is essentially to perform a simulation process with the support of computational technique before fabrication and manufacture. To considerably minimize the total cost, different numerical algorithms derived from electromagnetic theory, have been improved for analysis and energy harvesting. Various numerical methods, such as the finite difference time domain method (FDTD) [145], [146], the finite element method (FEM) [16], the method of moment (MoM) [147] and the geometrical theory of diffraction (GTD) [148], have been traditionally utilized. The FDTD is capable of discrete Maxwell's equations in time domain and exchanging the partial differential equation with the various equation to make numerical computation existing. The FEM depends on discretion of the operational different equation, to analyze the Eigen function in EM environment. The MoM discretizes the integral equation for numerical computations. As the integral equation needs the conditions of the radial boundary condition, MoM is frequently utilized to resolve the open-boundary problem. The GTD employs the geometrical optical theory, with the aid of the scattering rays, to solve the scattering problem commonly in superior frequencies of microwave spectrum. In this study, the FDTD method is applied for optimizing the energy harvesters with effective results.

3.3 Advantages of FDTD method

The FDTD numerical method is one of the most significant widened instruments for analyzing EM fields and studying their interaction with material structure, appreciations to adaptability with applications ranging from

bio-and nanophotonic, microwave communication devices, or geological and medical applications. The best valuable feature of this model is time domain dependence. Hence, the result of the computational simulation could involve a broadband wide range of frequencies with a single run. Moreover, the FDTD method is very effective in applications based on resonant frequencies or broadband results are required. Further ,precise modeling of a broad array of nonlinear media (as a result of magnetic structures and linear and nonlinear dielectric) could to be readily simulated [18].

An additional advantage of the FDTD model method is that all the EM-field components are exactly determined with high stability in calculations. Therefore, Plasmonic waveguide could be stimulated where all EM-field components are significant. Moreover, the FDTD method has the capability of defining nonlinear behaviors, arbitrary shapes and inhomogeneous properties. On top of that, the FDTD method suggests a simplified approach to visualize and optimize the real-time pictures of the electromagnetic wave.

3.4 Overview of FDTD method

The computational numerical simulations of our device are based upon the FDTD model. Therefore, a brief review of this FDTD method is essential to achieve the handling tricks in utilizing the software package. Modeling isotropic media is manipulated and non-dispersive as an example for following the steps of the FDTD algorithm [18], [19]. The time-dependent Maxwell's equations in free space are used as follows

$$\frac{\partial E}{\partial t} = \frac{1}{\epsilon_0} \nabla \times \frac{\partial H}{\partial t} \quad (3.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial H}{\partial t} = - \frac{1}{\mu_0} \nabla \times \frac{\partial E}{\partial t} \quad (3.2)$$

Where E and H are spatial vectors. For generalization, one-dimension equations of E_x and H_y are considered below,

$$\frac{\partial E_x}{\partial t} = - \frac{1}{\epsilon_0} X \nabla \frac{\partial H_y}{\partial z} \quad (3.3)$$

$$\frac{\partial H_y}{\partial t} = - \frac{1}{\mu_0} X \nabla \frac{\partial E_x}{\partial z} \quad (3.4)$$

Equation (3.3) and (3.4) represent a plane wave with an electric component adjusted in x direction, and its magnetic component is adjusted in y direction, travelling in the z direction.

These equations can be discretized with time step of Δt in the following form

$$\frac{E_x^{n+\frac{1}{2}}(k) - E_x^{n-\frac{1}{2}}(k)}{\Delta t} = - \frac{1}{\epsilon_0} X \frac{H_y^n(k+\frac{1}{2}) - H_y^n(k-\frac{1}{2})}{\Delta x} \quad (3.5)$$

$$\frac{H_y^{n+1}(k+\frac{1}{2}) - H_y^n(k+\frac{1}{2})}{\Delta t} = - \frac{1}{\mu_0} X \frac{E_x^{n+\frac{1}{2}}(k+1) - E_x^{n+\frac{1}{2}}(k)}{\Delta x} \quad (3.6)$$

Equations (3.5) and (3.6) can be reorganized in an iterative algorithm

$$E_x^{n+\frac{1}{2}}(k) = E_x^{n-\frac{1}{2}}(k) - \frac{\Delta t}{\epsilon_0 \Delta x} [H_y^n(k + \frac{1}{2}) - H_y^n(k - \frac{1}{2})] \quad (3.7)$$

$$H_y^{n+1}(k + \frac{1}{2}) = H_y^n(k + \frac{1}{2}) - \frac{\Delta t}{\mu_0 \Delta x} [E_x^{n+\frac{1}{2}}(k + 1) - E_x^{n+\frac{1}{2}}(k)] \quad (3.8)$$

The meshed cell size Δx is determined by the time step which is provided by the following equation, $\Delta t = \frac{\Delta x}{2c_0}$

where c_0 is the speed of light in free space. Time dependent Maxwell's equation in three dimensions, is given by

$$\frac{\partial D}{\partial t} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\epsilon_0 \mu_0}} \nabla \times H \quad (3.9)$$

where $D = \epsilon E$

$$\text{and } \frac{\partial H}{\partial t} = -\frac{1}{\sqrt{\epsilon_0 \mu_0}} \nabla \times E \quad (3.10)$$

A close study of Yee cell in FDTD algorithm [149], six scalar equations are produced as follows:

Fig.3.1: Yee cell utilized by a FDTD algorithm [149].

$$\frac{\partial D_x}{\partial t} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\epsilon_0 \mu_0}} \left(\frac{\partial H_z}{\partial y} - \frac{\partial H_y}{\partial z} \right) \quad (3.11)$$

$$\frac{\partial D_y}{\partial t} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\epsilon_0 \mu_0}} \left(\frac{\partial H_x}{\partial z} - \frac{\partial H_z}{\partial x} \right) \quad (3.12)$$

$$\frac{\partial D_z}{\partial t} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\epsilon_0 \mu_0}} \left(\frac{\partial H_y}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial H_x}{\partial y} \right) \quad (3.13)$$

$$\frac{\partial H_x}{\partial t} = \frac{-1}{\sqrt{\epsilon_0 \mu_0}} \left(\frac{\partial E_z}{\partial y} - \frac{\partial E_y}{\partial z} \right) \quad (3.14)$$

$$\frac{\partial H_y}{\partial t} = \frac{-1}{\sqrt{\epsilon_0 \mu_0}} \left(\frac{\partial E_x}{\partial z} - \frac{\partial E_z}{\partial x} \right) \quad (3.15)$$

$$\frac{\partial H_z}{\partial t} = \frac{-1}{\sqrt{\epsilon_0 \mu_0}} \left(\frac{\partial E_y}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial E_x}{\partial y} \right) \quad (3.16)$$

The initial step to estimate the finite difference approximation depends on differentiating Eqs (3.1) and (3.2). As an example: the finite difference approximations are produced as follows,

$$\begin{aligned} D_z^{n+\frac{1}{2}} \left(i, j, k + \frac{1}{2} \right) &= D_z^{n+\frac{1}{2}} \left(i, j, k - \frac{1}{2} \right) + \frac{\Delta t}{\Delta x \sqrt{\epsilon_0 \mu_0}} [H_y^n \left(i + \frac{1}{2}, j, k + \frac{1}{2} \right) \\ &- H_y^n \left(i - \frac{1}{2}, j, k + \frac{1}{2} \right) - H_x^n \left(i, j + \frac{1}{2}, k + \frac{1}{2} \right) \\ &+ H_x^n \left(i, j - \frac{1}{2}, k + \frac{1}{2} \right)] \end{aligned} \quad (3.17)$$

$$\begin{aligned} H_z^{n+\frac{1}{2}} \left(i + \frac{1}{2}, j + \frac{1}{2}, k \right) &= H_z^n \left(i + \frac{1}{2}, j + \frac{1}{2}, k \right) + \frac{-\Delta t}{\Delta x \sqrt{\epsilon_0 \mu_0}} [E_y^{n+\frac{1}{2}} \left(i + \frac{1}{2}, j + \frac{1}{2}, k \right) \\ &- E_y^{n+\frac{1}{2}} \left(i, j + \frac{1}{2}, k \right) - E_x^{n+\frac{1}{2}} \left(i + \frac{1}{2}, j + 1, k \right) \\ &+ E_x^{n+\frac{1}{2}} \left(i + \frac{1}{2}, j, k \right)] \end{aligned} \quad (3.18)$$

3.5 Frequency - dependent materials in FDTD Method

The properties of both dielectric and metal materials are considerably different in microwaves and/or low frequencies than inside the optical scale. The dielectric materials with relative permittivity [18] that changes with the frequency can be expressed as

$$\epsilon_r(\omega) = 1 + \chi + \frac{Ne^2}{\epsilon_0 m_0} \frac{1}{(\omega_0^2 + \omega^2 - i\gamma\omega)} = \epsilon_{r1} + i\epsilon_{r2} \quad (3.19)$$

$$\epsilon_{r1}(\omega) = 1 + \chi + \frac{Ne^2}{\epsilon_0 m_0} \frac{(\omega_0^2 - \omega^2)}{(\omega_0^2 - \omega^2)^2 + \gamma\omega} \quad (3.20)$$

$$\epsilon_{r2}(\omega) = \frac{Ne^2}{\epsilon_0 m_0} \frac{\gamma\omega}{(\omega_0^2 - \omega^2)^2 + (\gamma\omega)^2} \quad (3.21)$$

where χ , N , m_0 , ϵ_0 , γ and ω_0 are electric susceptibility, the total number of atoms per unit volume, the electron mass, dielectric electric constant coefficient, rate of dumping, and resonant frequency, respectively. The relative permittivity up to microwave band has an efficient real part which has the imaginary part equal to zero. As the frequency changes near the infrared region, even in the optical range and ultraviolet frequency bands, the imaginary part is more than zero. Hence, entirely relative permittivity is a frequency-changing complex function; both real and imaginary parts are positive, corresponding to the measured data.

The Drude model can be employed to explain the metal in optical frequencies, plasmonic material with a negative real part of its permittivity – which is various from that of a dielectric in optical frequencies. The real part ϵ_{r1} characterizes the energy that can be stored in the material, while the imaginary part ϵ_{r2} arises for the loss of energy in the materials. Typically, a dielectric material in the optical band dissipates power as a consequence of the positive imaginary part ϵ_{r2} of its permittivity. On the other hand, the real part ϵ_{r1} is

higher than that in microwave band, which implies that it can make the effective wavelength minor than that in the lesser band. For example, the real ϵ_{r1} is still positive, this causes the dielectric material a resonator in the optical band, which is various from plasmonic material whose real part is negative. Accordingly, no EM-wave can penetrate into plasmonic. A metal is frequently behaved as a plasmonic material in the optical spectrum. The plasma frequency [18] as a purpose of permittivity of a plasmonic material, can be modeled as

$$\omega_p = \sqrt{\frac{Ne^2}{m\epsilon_0}} \quad (3.22)$$

Related to gas plasma, the Drude model is utilized to express the plasmonic material. The valuable permittivity [18] of a plasmonic material is complex, and can be extracted as

$$\epsilon_p = \epsilon_0 \left[1 - \frac{\omega_p^2}{\omega(1+i\gamma)} \right] \quad (3.23)$$

Where γ symbolizes the damping effect. The conductivity [18] is expressed by

$$\sigma_p = i \frac{\epsilon_0 \omega_p^2}{(1+i\gamma)} \quad (3.24)$$

The FDTD method for a plasmonic material adapts the frequency-dependent permittivity data. Built on the Drude model [150], the first order estimate in one dimension is given by

$$\epsilon(\omega) = \epsilon_\infty + \frac{\epsilon_s - \epsilon_\infty}{1 - j\omega\tau} = \frac{D_z(\omega)}{E_z(\omega)} \quad (3.25)$$

Where τ is the Debye relaxation time constant, and $(\epsilon_s$ and $\epsilon_\infty)$ is $((0)$ and $(\infty))$.

Thus, the FDTD equation can be written as

$$E_z^{n+1}(k) = \frac{\Delta t + 2\tau}{2\tau\varepsilon_\infty + \varepsilon_s\Delta t} D_z^{n+1}(k) + \frac{\Delta t - 2\tau}{2\tau\varepsilon_\infty + \varepsilon_s\Delta t} D_z^{n-1}(k) + \frac{2\tau\varepsilon_\infty - \varepsilon_s\Delta t}{2\tau\varepsilon_\infty + \varepsilon_s\Delta t} E_z^n(k) \quad (3.26)$$

The second order approximation in one dimension is given by

$$\varepsilon(\omega) = \varepsilon_\infty + \frac{\omega_0^2(\varepsilon_s - \varepsilon_\infty)}{\omega^2 + j2\omega\delta - \omega_0^2} = \frac{D_z(\omega)}{E_z(\omega)} \quad (3.27)$$

Where ω_0 is the resonant frequency and δ is the damping coefficient. The FDTD equation is thus obtained by:

$$E_z^{n+1}(k) = \frac{\omega_0^2\Delta t^2 + 2\delta\Delta t + 2}{\omega_0^2\Delta t^2\varepsilon_s + 2\delta\Delta t\varepsilon_\infty + 2\varepsilon_\infty} D_z^{n+1} - \frac{4D_z^n - 4\varepsilon_\infty E_z^n}{\omega_0^2\Delta t^2\varepsilon_s + 2\delta\Delta t + 2\varepsilon_\infty} E_z^n + \frac{\omega_0^2\Delta t^2 - 2\delta\Delta t + 2}{\omega_0^2\Delta t^2\varepsilon_s + 2\delta\Delta t\varepsilon_\infty + 2\varepsilon_\infty} D_z^{n-1} - \frac{\omega_0^2\Delta t^2\varepsilon_s + 2\delta\Delta t\varepsilon_\infty + 2\varepsilon_\infty}{\omega_0^2\Delta t^2\varepsilon_s + 2\delta\Delta t\varepsilon_\infty + 2\varepsilon_\infty} E_z^{n-1} \quad (3.28)$$

With the computed electrical field, the voltage is taken by the line integral as follows:

$$V = \int E \cdot dl \quad (3.29)$$

Correspondingly, the current is calculated by integrating the H field along the closed path

$$I = \oint H \times dl \quad (3.30)$$

3.6 Boundary conditions

For a cell discretization, electric field, magnetic field and material parameters are generally kept in the computer memory for accurate numerical

calculations. Temporarily, identifiable boundaries are essential for reducing the computational domain and gaining accurate results throughout the FDTD simulations. Consequently, the FDTD model needs boundary constraints for dispensation. The boundary conditions (BCs) [151] are frequently dependent on the device under study. There are numerous BCs that are normally applied in FDTD simulations. In this thesis, periodic PBCs (of effectively infinite periodicity) are utilized for simulating nano structured SCs in usual and NWSCs in specific. The periodic BC will decrease the computational domain to one-unit cell only. Moreover, the perfect matched layer (PML) is used for modeling single NW SCs with open domains.

3.6.1 Periodic boundary conditions (PBCs)

PBCs are generally utilized when both the physical structure (geometry) of interest and the EM-fields are together periodically repeated. The periodicity probably in one or two directions. To simulate a NW SC structure which is periodic in two directions (x and y axis planes) but not essentially in the third one (z plane), PBCs are employed in two directions only. The PBCs tolerate the calculation of the response, characterizing the whole system, throughout simulating only one-unit cell. Once the simulation runs, the PBCs simply copy the EM fields that arise at one side of the simulation and insert them at the other side. Literature express that PBCs are normally applied in FDTD and FEM, where the relations between the fields can be cheerfully included. Periodic structure geometry can be gladly shaped by reflecting a rectangular-shaped unit cell; while standard normal incident illumination only is considered [18]. These unit cells can be arrayed in rectangular-lattice of NWAs, as well as in triangular or hexagonal arrays. Figures 3.2 (a), (b) and (c) represent a top view of square, triangular and hexagonal nanowire lattices symbolizing unit cells of the nanowires with periodic boundary conditions. These designs are periodic in the two dimensions of x and y axis planes.

Fig.3.2: upper view of Si nanowire with (a) square lattice (b) triangular lattice (c) hexagonal lattice. Spotted squares signify unit cells of each geometric structure with periodic boundary conditions.

3.6.2 Perfectly matched layers (PML)

For the simulation of a NWSCs, there is a different boundary conditions for simulating open domains. The simulation of NWSCs (harvesters) basically emphasizes upon the absorption inside the absorbing materials and not the far-field of the scattering from the structure geometry where, the employment of PMLs is realizable. A PML is an unnatural dielectric medium with a steady variation of its properties following to high attenuation and low reflection. The PML is frequently applied to truncate the computational domain in numerical methods to simulate difficulties with open boundaries, mainly in the FDTD and FEM methods. The PML boundaries showed to be more forceful compared to the prior methods for instance the ABC and PBC. The key property of PML is that it utilizing an imaginary electrical layer which allows it to absorb and attenuate the output wave at frequencies and different angles. This property basically tolerates the PML to powerfully absorb outgoing waves from the core of a computational region exclusive of reflecting them back into the core [152], [153].

In 1994, Berenger [154] set the foundations for the PML method, utilized initially with Maxwell's equations. Since that time, there have been various interacted reformulations of PML for both Maxwell's equations. In addition to, the other wave equations. Berenger's formulation is recognized as "split-field PML", due to it splits the electromagnetic fields into two imaginary fields in the PML region. An advanced formulation which is more popular because of its efficiency and simplicity is known as the uniaxial PML or UPML, in which the PML is expressed as an unnatural anisotropic absorbing material. Both Berenger's formulation and UPML were originally derived through manual formation of the conditions below where incident plane waves do not reflect from the PML interface edge from a homogeneous medium [152], [153].

3.7 Lumerical FDTD solutions

Numerical analysis of the NWs is operated utilized FDTD software package established via Lumerical software package. This software package is efficient in evaluating and analyzing the interaction of ultraviolet (UV), visible and IR radiation with the nanostructures. In this thesis, only spectrum from 300 nm to 1100 nm was employed in simulating SiNWs. The FDTD software package is based on the same general procedure for defining the FDTD solution [155]. The algorithm divided the discretized Maxwell's equations into two independent series of equations disposed of three vector quantities that can only be solved in the x-y axis plane. The transverse electric (TE) equations contain the x and y components of the electric field and the z component of the magnetic field, where as the transverse magnetic (TM) equations contain the z electric field component and the x and y magnetic field components. The FDTD package applied a rectangular Cartesian coordinate mesh like a computational domain. At each mesh specific point, the electric and magnetic fields are calculated and analyzed. To extract an accurate result, a lesser mesh is required utilized on the expense of simulation time and memory conditions.

This software package supports rapid prototyping and extremely accurate simulations, therefore decreasing reliance upon expensive experimental prototypes, heading to a nearer assessment of design concepts and specific geometric structures [155].

3.8 How to avoid the divergence in FDTD simulation?

The divergence of computed fields normally leads to initial termination of the simulation procedure. The electromagnetic field divergence is qualified to the stability factor D_t or to the PML boundary conditions. Consequently, a number of achievable solutions to resolve this problem are proposed [156].

3.8.1 D_t stability

Based on the Courant stability standard, it was obligatory to fix a time step lesser than the step computed from the mesh size. Furthermore, in the situation of dispersive materials, once the physical geometric structures and interfaces are involved in the simulation, a minor time step is necessary to avoid the divergence of the fields. When the dielectric function of dispersive materials is not well fit with the multi-coefficient model utilized by the software to resolve the Maxwell equations, D_t instability appears. Alternatively, multi-coefficient models, mainly those which depend on a set of basic functions that express Drude, Debye or Lorentz models, should be utilized to fit the dispersion profiles of certain materials. When dt is close to the maximum theoretical limit, a great mesh aspect ratio (higher than 5) forms another realizable reason of instability [157].

3.8.2 PML considerations

In order to get the maximum accurate results, it is advised to extend the physical structures throughout the PML boundary conditions to decrease the reflections from the PMLs. On the other hand, this can affect the simulation to diverge for some dispersive materials like metals. This problem can be

resolved by rising the PML layers and reducing the sigma factor related with the layer absorption exclusive of influencing the PML performance. Moreover, the mesh size can be refined [158].

3.9 The electrical simulator

Fig.3.3: Simulation strategy of nanostructured solar cell.

The electrical simulation numerically determines how the photo-generated electron-hole pairs can be collected at the electrical contacts and influence to the output electrical power. By the way, the carrier generation profile rate of the optical simulation for optimum geometrical parameters of proposed design is then imported into the electrical simulation to investigate the internal device physics. The electrical simulation is carried out utilizing finite element method via Lumerical software package [159]. The spatially optical generation rate $g(\vec{r}, \lambda)$ can be taken from the optical absorption $A(\vec{r}, \lambda)$ of the suggested design using:

$$g(\vec{r}, \lambda) = A(\vec{r}, \lambda) I(\lambda) \lambda / hc \quad (3.31)$$

The generation rate of total optical field within the proposed design is calculated employing the spectral integration [86], which is imported into the continuity equation as the generation term. The coupled nonlinear equations of semiconductor (drift-diffusion equations and Poisson continuity) are numerically solved simultaneously using finite element method via Lumerical device software package [160] to obtain the electrical properties of the suggested design. The electrons and holes continuity equations are [161]:

$$\frac{\partial(n)}{\partial t} = G_n - R_n + \frac{1}{q} \nabla \cdot \vec{J}_n \quad (3.32)$$

$$\frac{\partial(p)}{\partial t} = G_p - R_p - \frac{1}{q} \nabla \cdot \vec{J}_p \quad (3.33)$$

where $(\vec{J}_n$ and $\vec{J}_p)$ and $(G_n$ and $G_p)$ are the total current densities and optical generation rates of electrons and holes, respectively. The local recombination terms n and p are the respective electron and hole recombination rates based on Shockley-Read-Hall recombination, radiative recombination and auger recombination. The current density terms that are imported to the continuity equations can be obtained as the summation of diffusion and drift currents [162]:

$$\vec{J}_n = q\mu_n \vec{E} + qD_n \nabla n \quad (3.34)$$

$$\vec{J}_p = q\mu_p \vec{E} - qD_p \nabla p \quad (3.35)$$

Here μ_n and μ_p are the carrier mobility of electrons and holes, and D_n and D_p denote diffusion constant of the electrons and holes. Further, \vec{E} is the electric field, and q is the elementary charge. The Poisson equation [162] is obtained by:

$$\nabla \cdot \vec{E} = -q(p - n + N_D - N_A) \quad (3.36)$$

Where N_D and N_A are the net ionized dopant density for donors and acceptors.

3.10 Summary

In this chapter, A survey of the numerical techniques for modeling both optical energy harvesting and electrical characterization are depicted. The basics principles and benefits of the FDTD method is well discussed. Moreover, the applied boundary conditions in this thesis are explained.

Chapter (4)
Results of Highly Efficient
Nanopyramid Solar Cell

Chapter 4: Highly Efficient Nanopyramid Solar Cell

In this chapter, a proposed design of modified nanopyramid is discussed and analyzed in details for solar cells applications. The Lumerical 3D finite difference time domain (FDTD) and Lumerical Device software packages is utilized to study and tune the geometrical parameters of the modified nanopyramid solar cells. The FDTD software tool solves the Maxwells equations in 3D depending on the FDTD method, while Lumerical Device solves drift-diffusion equations and Poisson continuity. The optical absorption of proposed conical modified nanopyramid structures has been reported using 3D-FDTD method. Moreover, the geometrical parameters of the suggested modified nanopyramid are adjusted to maximize the optical absorption and consequently the ultimate efficiency. In addition, the electrical performance analysis of the proposed structure including doping concentration, junction thickness and Shockley-Read-Hall recombination are also investigated.

4.1 Introduction

Light trapping technique based on nanostructures is the most promising way to increase the light absorption through TF SCs [123]. Recently, Cruz-Campa *et al.* [163] have designed, and fabricated a crystalline Si SC with 14 μm thickness, 250 μm wide and high PCE of 14.9. Such design is thinner 10–15 times than the traditional commercial c-Si SCs. Additionally, Yoon *et al.* [164] increased the PCE up to ~17.5% using luminescent solar concentrators within 15 μm thick c-Si solar cells embedded in luminescent waveguides. Li *et al.* [165] have also introduced a nanopyramid structure in ultrathin a-Si/c-Si tandem SC. Such a design produced conversion efficiency of 13.3% using only 8 μm of silicon. Further, Mavrokefalos *et al.* [72] designed Si SC with nanopyramid grating with J_{sc} of 37.5 mA/cm^2 in 10 μm , which is comparable

to 37.2 mA/cm² of bulk Si SC counterpart. Furthermore, nanowire (NW) [134], nanopyramid [97], [160], nanocone (NC) [166], [167], nanofunnel [168], [169], NHs [170], multi-diameter nanopillars [171] and dual-diameter nanoholes [172] are also studied to improve the light trapping of SCs.

In this research work, a modified nanopyramid SC is suggested to improve the absorption capabilities of thin film SC. The 3D finite difference time domain (FDTD) method is employed to characterize the optical performance of the reported design. Further, the finite element method is used for the electrical characterizations of the modified SC via Lumerical software package [17]. The conventional nanopyramid depends on the gradient optical density which could couple the light into the active layer of the SC. If a flat surface area is obtained at the bottom of the nanopyramids due to fabrication imperfection, the surface reflection will be increased [173]. However, the reported design consists of a nanopyramid part above a nanorectangular unit. Therefore, a cavity will result in between the adjacent nanopyramids which improves the light absorption over the whole spectral range. Further, the nanopyramid unit could absorb lower wavelength [173], while the nanorectangular part will absorb the higher wavelengths. Therefore, the combination between nanopyramid and nanorectangular units achieve broadband absorption enhancement. The proposed design exhibits two folded benefits: broadband optical absorption, and superior ultimate efficiency due to the combined effects of nanopyramid and nanorectangular shapes. The reported design shows an ultimate efficiency of 40.93 % and J_{sc} of 33.49 mA/cm² with an improvement of 28.3% over the conventional nanopyramid. Further, the suggested SC with p-i-n axial doping achieves V_{oc} of 0.57 volt, J_{sc} of 28.42 mA/cm² and PCE of 13.3% which outperform the conventional nanopyramid SC of 0.559, 19.6 mA/cm² and 8.95%, respectively. The enhancements in the optical and electrical efficiencies are attributed to multiple scattering wave interference, coupling effect, Fabry-Perot resonance

[174], Bloch resonance, guided mode resonance and microcavity effect between adjacent nanostructures.

It should be noted that the conventional nanopyramid depends on the fill factor ($FF=A/P$) where A is the lattice constant and P is the periodicity as shown in the following figure 4.1.a [173]. If the FF is not equal 1, there must be some flat surface at the bottom of the nanopyramids. These flat surfaces would increase the surface reflection as shown in figure 4.2.b . Secondly, compared to other nanostructures such as nanowire, the nanopyramids could couple well to incident light because the optical density varies gradually. If the filling factor is not 1, there would be a sharp change of the optical density at the bottom of the nanopyramids, which may decrease the absorption. However, the reported design consists of a nanopyramid part above a nanorectangular unit. Therefore, a cavity will result in between the adjacent nanopyramids which improves the light absorption over the whole spectral range. Further, the nanopyramid unit could absorb lower wavelength, while the rectangular part will absorb the higher wavelengths. Therefore, the combination between nanopyramid and nano-rectangle units results in broadband absorption enhancement. The proposed designs exhibit two folded benefits: broadband optical absorption, and superior ultimate efficiency due to the combined effects of nanopyramid and nano-rectangle shapes.

Fig.4.1: (a) 3D representation of conventional nanopyramid SC and (b) The short circuit current as a function of the filling factor FF [173].

4.2 Optical and electrical simulation strategy

In this investigation, we study the optical and electrical characteristics of the modified nanopyramid SC shown in Fig4.2(a). The reported design consists of a nanopyramid part above a nanorectangle unit. The nanopyramid has height (h_p) with bottom base width (B_p), while the lower rectangle has height (h_r) and lattice width (W_r). Fig4.2(b) displays a 3D schematic diagram of the modified pyramid design. The suggested grating SC unit cell is shown in Fig4.1 (a) with periodicity (P). In order to increase the optical path length and the probability of the active layer to absorb more photons, the modified nanopyramid design is positioned over silicon substrate with thickness ($T=2000$ nm) and silver back reflector with thickness of 400 nm. The finite-difference time-domain (FDTD) method via Lumerical software package [17] is employed to calculate the absorption and generation rate for the studied design. The complex dielectric constant of the Ag and Si are directly taken from the Lumerical software data base using Palik models. In this study, periodic boundary conditions were used in X and Y directions around the unit cell to model the periodic array structure. However, perfectly matched layers

are used in z direction. The modified SC is illuminated from the top by a plane wave with a wavelength range from 300 nm to 1100 nm (typical absorption region of Si) to model the sunlight. This is mainly due to the weak spectrum through $\lambda < 300$ nm and the silicon cannot absorb photons anymore at $\lambda > 1100$ nm. Two flat power monitors are utilized to calculate the reflection, absorption and hence the transmission. The reflection monitor M_1 is placed above the modified design while the transmission monitor M_2 is put between the surface of the silicon substrate and the silver back reflector. In order to obtain high accuracy, fine mesh size of $5 \times 5 \times 5$ nm³ is used. This means that the mesh length is equal to 1/60 of the shortest wavelength [168] with a unit cell length of 6000 nm.

Fig.4.2: schematic diagram of the modified pyramid SC (a) 2D unit cell and (b) 3D representation

The absorption within the reported design can be calculated from energy conservation in Eqn4.1

$$A(\lambda) = M_1(\lambda) - M_2(\lambda) \quad (4.1)$$

To quantify the broadband absorption capabilities of the modified design within the whole spectrum, the ultimate efficiency (η) [168] is defined as

$$\eta = \frac{\int_{300}^{\lambda_g} F_s(\lambda) \frac{\lambda}{\lambda_g} A(\lambda) d\lambda}{\int_{300}^{4000} F_s(\lambda) d\lambda} \quad (4.2)$$

Where λ is the incident light wavelength, λ_g is the Si wavelength bandgap of 1100 nm, and $F_s(\lambda)$ is the photon flux density ASTM at air mass AM1.5 [162], [169]. The short circuit current density (J_{sc}) [168] can be calculated by

$$\begin{aligned} J_{sc} &= \int_{300nm}^{\lambda_g} F_s(\lambda) A(\lambda) \frac{e\lambda}{hc} d\lambda \\ &= \eta \frac{e\lambda_g}{hc} \int_{300nm}^{4000nm} F_s(\lambda) d\lambda = 81.83 * \eta \text{ (mA/cm}^2\text{)} \end{aligned} \quad (4.3)$$

Where e , c and h are the electron charge, speed of light and the plank constant, respectively. To quantify the device performance of the proposed solar cell, the position-dependent generation rate $g(\vec{r}, \lambda)$ [160], [162] is obtained from the 3D FDTD optical modeling as given by

$$g(\vec{r}, \lambda) = A(\vec{r}, \lambda) F_s(\lambda) \lambda / hc \quad (4.4)$$

Where $A(\vec{r}, \lambda)$ is the absorption of suggested design.

For the electrical simulation, the optical generation rates are imported into the finite-element method using Lumerical device software package. In this study, the carrier continuity equations coupled with Poisson's equation are solved. To make the simulation more realistic, the doping-dependent mobility, radiative, Auger, and SRH recombination are taken into consideration in the device electrical simulation [169]. The power conversion efficiency (PCE) can be calculated according to the following equation.

$$\text{PCE} = \frac{J_{sc} V_{oc} FF}{P_{in}} \quad (5.5)$$

Where P_{in} is the incident power at AM 1.5, FF is the fill factor defined as ($FF = P_{max}/J_{sc} V_{oc}$) and V_{oc} is the open circuit voltage and P_{max} is maximum power.

4.3 Results and discussion

4.3.1 Optical analysis

Figure 4.3 (a) shows the absorption spectra of the conventional nanopyramid design and the reported modified nanopyramid SC. In this study, the B_p and h_p are taken from Ref [160], [173], [175]. The initial parameters of the nanopyramid and modified nanopyramid designs are listed in table 1. It is revealed from Fig.4.3 (a) that the modified nanopyramid has higher absorption in shorter and longer wavelengths than the conventional nanopyramid counterpart. Figure 4.3 (b) shows the ultimate efficiency and the short circuit current density of the studied designs. The corresponding ultimate efficiency and the short circuit current density are equal to 39.6% and 32.4 mA/cm², respectively. Therefore, the modified nanopyramid offers an overall enhancement of 22.2% over the conventional nanopyramid counterparts. Further, the modified nanopyramid design has a short-circuit current density of 32.4 mA/cm², which is greater than 26.1 mA/cm² of the conventional nanopyramid design. To further understand the physics behind the optical absorption enhancement in the modified nanopyramid SC, the electric field profiles are analyzed in detail. Figures 4.3 (c-e) exhibit the electric field profile at $\lambda=943$ nm through the planar, conventional design and modified SC respectively. It may be seen from these plots that the incident light is more penetrated and confined through the suggested design than the conventional nanopyramid which improves the light absorption and hence the ultimate efficiency. It is worth noting that the planar SCs have much lower absorption over the whole spectral range as shown in Fig.4.3(a). The planar structure

supports vertical Fabry-Perot mode resonances as revealed from Fig.4.3 (c). However, simple and double grating with periodic structures exhibit Bloch mode-like diffraction pattern corresponding to high absorption peaks. The periodic grating SC can have a profound effect on the nature of the dispersion relation and wavefunction of the absorber. It may be seen from Fig.4.2 that the proposed design has a 2D periodicity in x, and y directions. Such a periodicity supports electromagnetic waves that obey Bloch theorem [98]. This is evident from the absorption spectra of the suggested SC and the Bloch mode field plots at wavelengths of $\lambda=943$ nm as shown in Fig.4.3(e). The high absorption peaks with reduced linewidth shown in Fig.4.3 illustrate the photons longer lifetime trapping in the c-Si active layer [176]. It is also worth noting that the small extinction coefficient, interference effect at the top and bottom air/dielectric interfaces, coupling effect and Bloch resonance modes (caused by the periodical structures) could result in the oscillations in the absorption spectra in the long wavelength range for incident photon energy below 2.5 eV [177]. In this context, the modified nanopyramid structure has an effective index gradient which causes the reflection of the incident light at different depths from the air/silicon interface [160], [173]. Therefore, a minimized reflectance can be obtained by destructive interferences. Further, the modified nanopyramid causes an angular redistribution of the incident light which largely increases the optical path length in the SC active layer [160], [173]. Additionally, the combined effect from the front and rear nanostructures results in the absorption improvement over large band of wavelengths. This is due to the many cavities of the modified nanopyramid design which is different from the standard multilayer cavity of the planar SC film [160]. The strongly intensified resonant modes excited from the nanopyramid structure, facilitating light absorption in a broad spectral band.

Table 4.1. The initial geometrical parameters of the conventional nanopyramid [160], [173] and modified nanopyramid designs

Parameter	Description	Conventional nanopyramid	Modified nanopyramid
B_p	pyramid base	700 (nm)	700 (nm)
h_p	pyramid height	1200 (nm)	1200 (nm)
h_r	rectangle height	0 (nm)	400 (nm)
W_r	rectangle width	0 (nm)	1000 (nm)
T	substrate thickness	2000 (nm)	1600 (nm)
P	Periodicity	1400 (nm)	1400 (nm)

Fig.4.3: (a) Absorption spectra, (b) η and J_{sc} of planner, conventional nanopyramid SC, and modified nanopyramid SC. Electric field profiles are shown through the (c) planer, (d) conventional nanopyramid and (e) modified nanopyramid SC at $\lambda = 943\text{nm}$, respectively.

To further understand the physics behind the improved light trapping and hence the optical absorption in the modified nanopyramid SC, the electric field profiles is examined in detail at different wavelengths. Figures 4.4 (a-f) shows the electric field profile through rectangular grating SC, the conventional design and modified SC respectively at two wavelengths $\lambda=500$ nm and $\lambda=977$ nm. The reported design consists of a nanopyramid part above a nanorectangle unit. Therefore, a cavity will result in between the adjacent nanopyramids which improves the light absorption over the whole spectral range as shown in Fig.4.4. Further, the nanopyramid unit could absorb lower wavelength, while the rectangular part will absorb the higher wavelengths as shown in Fig.4.4(c) and 4.4(f). Therefore, the combination between nanopyramid and nano-rectangle units results in broadband absorption enhancement.

The proposed designs exhibit two folded benefits: broadband optical absorption, and superior ultimate efficiency due to the combined effects of nanopyramid and nanorectangular shapes. When plane light waves are incident on the grating surface structure, the incoming light wave is coupled with the waveguide mode by diffraction on the grating and resonance occurs; The resonance wavelength depends on the phase matching element of the grating layer [178]. The resonance wavelength depends on the grating parameters i.e., grating period, grating grooved height, structural line width and the refractive indices of materials and surroundings [178]. The grating structure can reduce the scattering and reflecting loss of light by providing interfaces to the incoming light to propagate and confine within the cell material [178]. This enhancement in light confinement by grating structure increases the efficiency of the solar cell by increasing its optical absorption [178]. For an efficient light confinement, the grating SC may be designed to support multiple resonances in all regions of the solar spectrum. This can be achieved by designing the grating structure having grating period less than the incident light wavelengths [178].

Fig.4.4: Electric field profiles of (a), (d) nanorectangular, (b), (e) nanopyramid and (c), (f) modified nanopyramid at $\lambda = 500nm$ and $\lambda = 977nm$.

The absorption enhancement through the modified nanopyramid design can be more explained based on the grating theory [179]. Figures 4.5(a) and 4.5(b) show the propagation direction and strength of the grating orders at $\lambda = 943$ nm for the studied designs. It is revealed from these figures that the intensity of the power transmittance diffraction orders of the conventional nanopyramid is greater than those of the modified nanopyramid. Therefore, the absorption of the modified pyramid is much higher than those of the conventional nanopyramid over the entire wavelength range. This enhancement is attributed to the novelty of the modified nanopyramid, which consists of nanopyramid and nanorectangular units. The incident light with different wavelengths can be effectively coupled into the active layer at different cross-sectional areas of

the different units of the nanopyramid bases. Therefore, a longer optical path length can be achieved than that occurs through the conventional nanopyramid. Consequently, the absorption and hence the short circuit current density are enhanced. Figure 4.5(c) shows the wavelength dependent grating order. It may be seen from this figure that the grating orders of the conventional nanopyramid and modified nanopyramid are nearly the same. However, the grating orders depend mainly on the incident wavelength, which is compatible with that reported in [179].

Fig.4.5: The propagation direction and strength of transmission diffraction orders of the (a) modified nanopyramid and (b) conventional nanopyramid at $\lambda = 943$ nm, and (c) number of diffraction orders versus wavelength.

In order to increase the absorption and minimize the reflection of the modified nanopyramid design, the geometrical parameters of the suggested design are studied thoroughly. The effect of the substrate thickness on the performance

of the modified SC is first studied as shown in Fig. 4.6 where, $h_r+T=2000$ nm to be comparable to the thickness of thin film SC [160], [173]. Figure 4.6(a) shows the variation of the ultimate efficiency with the rectangle height h_r , whereas the other parameters B_p , h_p , W_r , and P are fixed to 700 nm, 1200 nm, 1000 nm and 1400 nm, respectively. It may be seen from this figure that the ultimate efficiency is enhanced by increasing the nanorectangular height h_r from 0 nm to 300 nm. The front surface of modified nanopyramid design leads to significantly suppressed reflection due to a graded refractive index from air to silicon. Moreover, the multiple reflections of the photons caused by the nanopyramids contribute to the increase of the optical path length and the dwell time inside the active layer. This is also confirmed from Fig. 4.6(b) which illustrates the wavelength dependent absorption at different h_r values. Figure 4.6(c) and 4.6(d) show the electric field profiles in the xz plane at $h_r=100$ nm and $h_r=800$ nm, respectively at $\lambda=700$ nm. It may be seen that the incident light is more concentrated and confined through the suggested design at $h_r=800$ nm than at $h_r=100$ nm which is compatible with the ultimate efficiency shown in Fig.4.6(a). It is worth noting that the front grating acts as a phase grating. Therefore, the phase difference between the interfering waves is changed by varying the grating height where a phase difference of π results in the propagation of even diffraction orders. Hence, most of the light will propagate at large diffraction angles, which increases the optical path length of the light in the SC.

Fig.4.6: (a) Variation of the ultimate efficiency with the rectangle height h_r , (b) wavelength dependent absorption at different rectangle heights and steady state electric field profiles at $\lambda = 700$ nm for the modified nanopyramid at rectangle height of (c) $h_r=100$ nm and (d) $h_r=800$ nm.

The effect of the rectangle width W_r on the ultimate efficiency is also studied thoroughly. Figure 4.7(a) shows the variation of ultimate efficiency with different rectangle widths W_r . In this investigation, the other geometrical parameters are kept constant at $B_p=700$ nm, $h_p=1200$ nm, $h_r=800$ nm, $T=1200$ nm and $P=1400$ nm. As the rectangle width W_r is increased from 700 nm to 980 nm, the active material volume will be increased. Consequently, the ultimate efficiency and short circuit current density will be enhanced to 40.93% and 33.49 mA/cm², respectively. Additionally, as the rectangle width increases from 980 nm to 1200 nm, the ultimate efficiency decreases due to

the increase of the top flat area of the rectangle part which increases the reflection. This is confirmed by the wavelength dependent absorption shown in Fig 4.7(b) at different W_r values. The ultimate efficiency increases with increasing the rectangle width until $W_r=980$ nm because of Fabry-Perot cavity resonance and grating diffraction [180], [181]. As the rectangle width increases from 700 nm to 980 nm, the optical wave interference is enhanced where a destructive interference occurs for the reflected waves. Figures 4.7(c) and (d) show the xz field profiles at $\lambda=700$ nm at $W_r = 980$ nm and 1300 nm. It may be observed from these figures that a large part of light is coupled and confined at $W_r = 980$ nm. This is attributed to the absorption enhancement of the modified design with reduced reflection.

Fig.4.7: (a) Variation of the ultimate efficiency with the rectangle width W_r , (b) wavelength dependent absorption at different rectangle widths. The steady state electric field profiles at $\lambda= 700$ nm for the modified nanopyramid at (c) $W_r=980$ nm and (d) $W_r=1200$ nm.

Next, the effect of the nanopyramid base width B_p is studied at $h_p=1200\text{nm}$, $h_r=800\text{ nm}$, $W_r= 980$, $T=1200\text{ nm}$ and $P=1400\text{ nm}$. Figure 4.8(a) demonstrates the ultimate efficiency against the pyramid base B_p . It may be seen that the nanopyramid grating could efficiently couple the incident light since the optical density varies gradually [160], [173], [182]. It is revealed from Fig.4.8(a) that as B_p increases from 300 nm to 400 nm, the reflection decreases while the absorption increases. When the nanopyramid base is too small, the light will not have the ability for detecting the proposed nanostructures and hence the optical diffraction will be so weak. As the nanopyramid base increases the optical density variation and active materials are increased. Therefore, the ultimate efficiency and hence J_{sc} are increased. Maximum ultimate efficiency of 40.93 % and J_{sc} of 33.49 mA/cm² are obtained at $B_p=700\text{ nm}$. This is confirmed by the wavelength dependent absorption shown in Fig 6(b) at different B_p values. As the nanopyramid base is further increased from 400 nm 700 nm, the flat surface area of nanorectangular unite decreases. Figure 4.8(b) illustrates the wavelength dependent absorption at different nanopyramid base B_p . Figures 4.8(c) and 4.8(d) demonstrate the xz electric field profiles at $\lambda=700\text{ nm}$ at $B_p = 400\text{ nm}$ and 700 nm, respectively. Therefore, photons reflection between the nanopyramids decreases which increases the absorption and ultimate efficiencies. Table 2 shows the tuned geometrical parameters of the reported modified nanopyramid that will be used for the subsequent electrical simulations.

Table 4.2. The geometrical parameters of the conventional nanopyramid [160], [173] and modified nanopyramid designs

Parameter	Description	Conventional nanopyramid (nm)	Modified nanopyramid (nm)
B_p	pyramid base	700	700
h_p	pyramid height	1200	1200
h_r	rectangle height	0	800
W_r	rectangle width	0	980
T	substrate thickness	2000	1200
P	Periodicity	1400	1400

Fig.4.8: (a) Variation of the ultimate efficiency with the nanopyramid base B_p , (b) wavelength dependent absorption at different nanopyramid bases and steady state electric field profiles at $\lambda = 700$ nm for the modified nanopyramid at nanopyramid base of (c) $B_p = 700$ nm and (d) $B_p = 400$ nm.

4.3.2 Electrical analysis

The finite element method via Lumerical software package is employed to study and characterize the electrical performance of the reported design. Figure 4.9(a) and 4.9(b) show the schematic diagrams of the tuned modified nanopyramid and the conventional nanopyramid designs with p-i-n doping (p-type/intrinsic/n-type) mounted on Si substrate. The top contact of the modified nanopyramid is used as an emitter as shown in Fig.4.9. The geometrical parameters of the modified nanopyramid SC parameters are taken from table 2. The silicon material has a surface recombination velocity with the metal of 10^7 cm/s. In this study, the p-layer has a thickness of 400 nm while the n-layer has a thickness of 300 nm. The computational domain of the 3D charge solver has dimensions of $x = y = 1400$ nm while $z = 3500$ nm. In order to make the electrical simulation results more realistic, the radiative, Auger and SRH recombination are taken into consideration. The optical generation is imported in the Lumerical Device where the drift equation and Poisson equation are solved to analyze the electric characteristics of the modified nanopyramid design. The doping concentration of the p-type is 5×10^{18} cm⁻³, while the intrinsic i-type doping is equal to 10^{15} cm⁻³ [183], [184]. In this investigation, the electrical parameters are listed in Table 4.3.

Fig.4.9: Schematic diagram of a unit cell of the (a) modified nanopyramid design (b) conventional nanopyramid SC

Table 4.3. The electrical parameters of the modified nanopyramid unit cell [162].

Parameters	Description	Nominal value
μ_p	Hole mobility	470.5 cm ² /V.s
μ_n	Electron mobility	1471 cm ² /V.s
N_D	Donor concentration (<i>n</i> - doping)	10 ¹⁷ to 10 ²⁰ cm ⁻³
N_A	Acceptor concentration (<i>p</i> - doping)	5x10 ¹⁸ cm ⁻³
τ_n	Electron SRH recombination lifetime	3.3μs
τ_p	Hole SRH recombination lifetime	4 μs
$C_{n, \text{Auger}}$	Auger recombination of electrons for Silicon at 300K	2.8e ⁻³¹ cm ⁶ /s
$C_{p, \text{Auger}}$	Auger recombination of holes for Silicon at 300K	9.9e ⁻³¹ cm ⁶ /s
$C_{\text{radiative}}$	Radiative recombination coefficient for Silicon at 300K	1.6e ⁻¹⁴ cm ³ /s
SRV	surface recombination velocity	0-10 ⁶ cm/s

Figure 4.10(a) and 4.10(b) illustrate the current–voltage (J–V) curve and the power–voltage curve (PV curve) of conventional nanopyramid and the suggested modified nanopyramid, respectively. It may be observed from these figures that the proposed design shows better electrical efficiency than that of the conventional nanopyramid. The suggested design shows PCE of 13.3%, which is higher than that of the conventional nanopyramid by 48.6%. Additionally, the J_{sc} of the conventional and modified SCs are 19.6 mA/cm² and 28.42 mA/cm², respectively. The open circuit voltage and short circuit current density are increased to 0.57 volt and 28.42 mA/cm² by using the reported SC. The J_{sc} enhancement of the modified design is basically due to the optical generation of escalated electron hole pairs in comparison to the

conventional nanopyramid [183]–[185], as shown in Fig. 4.10(c) and 4.10(d). Table 4 summarizes the electrical performance parameters of the conventional nanopyramid and the proposed modified nanopyramid design.

Table 4.4: Electrical results of conventional nanopyramid and the modified nanopyramid SCs.

	J_{sc} (mA/cm ²)	V_{oc} (v)	FF	PCE %
Nanopyramid	19.6	0.559	0.815	8.95
Modified nanopyramid	28.42	0.57	0.817	13.3

Fig.4.10: (a) JV curve and (b) PV curve of nanopyramid and modified nanopyramid designs. The generation field profiles of the nanopyramid and the modified nanopyramid are shown in Fig.4.8 (b) and (c), respectively at $\lambda = 700$ nm.

Figure 4.11 shows (a) the J-V curve (b) the P-V curve for axial junction at different SRV values. It may be seen from this figure that at SRV = 0, the axial junction has high V_{oc} . Additionally, the SRV radically decreases the short circuit current density and open circuit voltage of the axial doped-based design. As the SRV increases from 0 to 10^6 cm/s, the J_{sc} and V_{oc} of the axial p-i-n junction structure decrease from 28.42 mA/cm² and 0.57 V to 5.21 mA/cm² and 0.19 V, respectively. Therefore, the axial junction in nanowire SCs is strongly affected by the SRV. This is due to the geometry of the axial p-i-n junction structure, where the minority carriers' depletion occurs through the entire modified nanopyramid (NW radius) owing to the SRV.

Fig.4.11: (a) JV curve and (b) PV curve at different surface recombination velocities

Figures 4.12(a) and 4.12(b) demonstrate the open circuit voltage (V_{oc}) and short circuit current density (J_{sc}) with the axial doping concentrations at N layer thickness of 300 nm and 2100 nm, respectively. In this study, the carrier life time is taken as 3.3 μ s for electrons and 4 μ s for holes. It may be seen from Fig.4.12(a) that at N layer thickness = 300 nm, the J_{sc} and V_{oc} are nearly constant at 28.42 mA/cm² and 0.57 v after doping concentration of 10^{17} cm⁻³. It is worth mentioning that the area exposed to the incident light is small (300 nm) consequently the effect of N type doping concentration has a slight effect

on J_{sc} as shown in Fig.4.12(a). However, at a thickness of 2100 nm, the J_{sc} and V_{oc} are decreased from 26.4 mA/cm² and 0.567 v to 10.56 mA/cm² and 0.549 v, respectively by increasing the doping concentration from 10¹⁸ cm⁻³ to 10²⁰ cm⁻³ as shown in Fig.4.12(b). As the doping concentration increases, the carrier life time decreases and the Auger recombination increases. Therefore, the J_{sc} and PCE are decreased. Therefore, PCE of 13.3% is almost constant at N layer thickness of 300 nm as shown in Fig.4.12(c). However, at thickness of 2100 nm, as the doping concentration is increased from 10¹⁷ to 10²⁰, the PCE is decreased from 11.72 % to 6.17 %. Figure 4.12(d) illustrates the variation of J_{sc} at different N layer thickness. It is evident from this figure that the N layer thickness ($N_D = 10^{20}$ cm⁻³) has a strong effect on the J_{sc} , especially at a thickness greater than 1300 nm. As the N layer thickness is increased from 1300 nm to 2100 nm, the J_{sc} decreases from 28.42 mA/cm² to 10.65 mA/cm². This is mainly attributed to the N layer thickness increase which decreases the i layer thickness. Therefore, the number of e-h pairs carriers and hence the J_{sc} flow in the SC and PCE are decreased.

2

Fig.4.12: Variation of the open circuit voltage (V_{oc}) and short circuit current density (J_{sc}) with N doping concentration (a) N layer thickness 300 nm (b) N layer thickness 2100 nm, (c) PCE of the modified nanopyramid at N layer thickness 300 nm and 2100 nm and (d) variation of the short circuit current density (J_{sc}) with the N layer thickness.

The suggested design can be fabricated through a series of lithography, dry, and wet etching steps as reported in [160], [186] for the conventional nanopyramid. In this context, Fig 4.13. Shows a flow chart of the fabrication process of the reported design.

Fig.4.13: A flow chart of the fabrication process of the reported design.

4.3 Summary

In this chapter, a proposed design of modified nanopyramid has been investigated and analyzed to enhance the light absorption inside proposed structure. The geometrical parameters of the proposed design were studied. In addition, the optical and electrical characteristics are included.

***Chapter (5) Conclusions
and future work***

Chapter 5: Conclusions and future work

5.1 Conclusions

The geometrical parameters of the suggested design are studied by using the 3-D FDTD to maximize the ultimate efficiency and J_{sc} , While the finite element analysis is utilized to analyze the electric properties such V_{oc} , F,F and PCE.

The numerical results indicate that the modified nanopyramid achieves an ultimate efficiency of 40.93% with an enhancement of 28.3% relative to the conventional nanopyramid. In addition, short circuit current density of 33.49 mA/cm² is achieved by the reported design. The studied modified nanopyramid enhances the optical absorption and decreases reflection due to multiple scattering wave interference, coupling effect, Fabry–Perot resonance, Bloch resonance, guided-mode resonance, and microcavity effect between adjacent nanostructures. The nanopyramid arrays suppress reflection due to their geometry with graded refractive index from air to silicon. The rectangular part will absorb the higher wavelengths. In addition, the electrical performance of the suggested modified nanopyramid is also examined. In the electrical analysis, junction geometry, the doping concentration, and Shockley-Read- Hall (SRH) recombination are taken into consideration. In this study, an axial p-i-n junction with intrinsic layer is used where the absorbed photons can generate electron – hole pairs. The generated charge carriers are separated and driven to the electrodes by the internal electric field provided by the n-and p-layers. The electrical simulations indicate that a PCE of 13.3% can be achieved using the suggested modified nanopyramid. A PCE of 13.3%, V_{oc} of 0.57 volt and J_{sc} of 28.42 mA/cm² can be achieved by using high quality silicon material.

5.2 Future work

We investigated in this thesis the optical and electrical properties of a novel structure modified nanopyramid. The geometrical parameters of the reported structure are optimized by utilizing 3- D FDTD method. Though, the maximum achieved PCE is 13.3% by using high-quality silicon material which still less than the theoretical efficiency limit. So, the future work will be focused on studying thermal properties of highly efficient solar cell and introducing new nanostructured perovskite and organic solar cell to achieve high power conversion efficiency.

References

Reference

- [1] Y. M. El-Toukhy, M. F. O. Hameed, M. Hussein, and S. S. A. Obayya, "Tapered Plasmonic Nanoantennas for Energy Harvesting Applications," in *Nanoplasmonics - Fundamentals and Applications*, InTech, 2017.
- [2] P. Nejat, F. Jomehzadeh, M. M. Taheri, M. Gohari, and M. Z. Muhd, "A global review of energy consumption, CO₂ emissions and policy in the residential sector (with an overview of the top ten CO₂ emitting countries)," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 43. Elsevier Ltd, pp. 843–862, 2015.
- [3] L. Olatomiwa, S. Mekhilef, M. S. Ismail, and M. Moghavvemi, "Energy management strategies in hybrid renewable energy systems: A review," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 62. Elsevier Ltd, pp. 821–835, 2016.
- [4] V. Khare, S. Nema, and P. Baredar, "Solar-wind hybrid renewable energy system: A review," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 58. Elsevier Ltd, pp. 23–33, 01-May-2016.
- [5] M. Aneke and M. Wang, "Energy storage technologies and real life applications – A state of the art review," *Applied Energy*, vol. 179. Elsevier Ltd, pp. 350–377, 01-Oct-2016.
- [6] T. D. Lee and A. U. Ebong, "A review of thin film solar cell technologies and challenges," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 70. Elsevier Ltd, pp. 1286–1297, 2017.
- [7] M. A. Green, K. Emery, Y. Hishikawa, W. Warta, and E. D. Dunlop, "(Version 4Solar cell efficiency tables5)," *Prog. Photovoltaics Res. Appl.*, vol. 23, no. 1, pp. 1–9, 2015.
- [8] S. Sinha and S. S. Chandel, "Review of software tools for hybrid renewable energy systems," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 32. pp. 192–205, Apr-2014.
- [9] Varun, I. K. Bhat, and R. Prakash, "LCA of renewable energy for electricity generation systems-A review," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 13, no. 5. pp. 1067–1073, Jun-2009.
- [10] N. L. Panwar, S. C. Kaushik, and S. Kothari, "Role of renewable energy sources in environmental protection: A review," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 15, no. 3. pp. 1513–1524, Apr-2011.
- [11] "Technology Guide: Principles - Applications - Trends - كتب Google." [Online]. Available: [https://books.google.com.eg/books?hl=ar&lr=&id=Tqlj-EpNj7cC&oi=fnd&pg=PA2&dq=\).+Technology+guide:+Principles-applications-trends&ots=u1PRsC2k02&sig=7srBxTAWwrx9hFcbAI9NZX1Ya3I&redir_esc=y#v=onepage&q=\). Technology guide%3A Principles-applications-trends&f=false](https://books.google.com.eg/books?hl=ar&lr=&id=Tqlj-EpNj7cC&oi=fnd&pg=PA2&dq=).+Technology+guide:+Principles-applications-trends&ots=u1PRsC2k02&sig=7srBxTAWwrx9hFcbAI9NZX1Ya3I&redir_esc=y#v=onepage&q=). Technology guide%3A Principles-applications-trends&f=false). [Accessed: 22-Sep-2019].
- [12] M. Guo, W. Song, and J. Buhain, "Bioenergy and biofuels: History, status, and

- perspective," *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.*, vol. 42, pp. 712–725, 2015.
- [13] X. Zhu and S. Sun, *Nanophotocatalysis and Environmental Applications*, no. April. 2019.
- [14] Y. Tian and C. Y. Zhao, "A review of solar collectors and thermal energy storage in solar thermal applications," *Appl. Energy*, vol. 104, no. Applied energy, pp. 538–553, 2013.
- [15] Z. Wu, "The effective energy transformation scheme as a special continuation approach to global optimization with application to molecular conformation," *SIAM J. Optim.*, vol. 6, no. 3, pp. 748–768, 1996.
- [16] A. Luque and S. Hegedus, *Handbook of Photovoltaic Science and Engineering*. 2011.
- [17] "High-Performance Photonic Simulation Software - Lumerical." [Online]. Available: <https://www.lumerical.com/>. [Accessed: 22-Sep-2019].
- [18] N. F. F. Areed, M. F. O. Hameed, and S. S. A. Obayya, "Highly sensitive face-shaped label-free photonic crystal refractometer for glucose concentration monitoring," *Opt. Quantum Electron.*, vol. 49, no. 1, Jan. 2017.
- [19] S. Obayya, M. F. O. Hameed, and N. F. F. Areed, *Computational Liquid Crystal Photonics*. 2016.
- [20] J. Chen and H. Mai, "A review of weakly conditional stable finite-difference time-domain method for modeling electromagnetic problems with fine structures," *Int. J. Numer. Model. Electron. Networks, Devices Fields*, vol. 31, no. 5, Sep. 2018.
- [21] M. G. Moharam, T. K. Gaylord, E. B. Grann, and D. A. Pommet, "Formulation for stable and efficient implementation of the rigorous coupled-wave analysis of binary gratings," *J. Opt. Soc. Am. A*, vol. 12, no. 5, pp. 1068–1076, May 1995.
- [22] P. Wangyang, Q. Wang, X. Wan, K. Hu, and K. Huang, "Optical absorption enhancement in silicon square nanohole and hybrid square nanowire-hole arrays for photovoltaic applications," *Opt. Commun.*, vol. 294, pp. 377–383, 2013.
- [23] X. Fan, W. Zheng, and D. J. Singh, "Light scattering and surface plasmons on small spherical particles," *Light: Science and Applications*, vol. 3. Nature Publishing Group, 06-Jun-2014.
- [24] E. Garnett and P. Yang, "Light trapping in silicon nanowire solar cells," *Nano Lett.*, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 1082–1087, Mar. 2010.
- [25] "Semiconductor Lasers: Fundamentals and Applications - كتب Google." [Online]. Available: [https://books.google.com.eg/books?hl=ar&lr=&id=sI5wAgAAQBAJ&oi=fnd&pg=PP1&dq=Baranov,+A.,+%26+Tournié,+E.+\(Eds.\).+\(2013\).+Semiconductor+Lasers:+Fundamentals+and+Applications.+Elsevier.&ots=M_G5Q2kVmM&sig=PtKCplj2v8i96mXS2u4EChoPR-0&redir_esc=y#v=onepage&q=Baranov%2C+A.%2C+%26+Tournié%2C+E.\(Eds.\).\(2013\).SemiconductorLasers%3AFundamentalsandApplications.](https://books.google.com.eg/books?hl=ar&lr=&id=sI5wAgAAQBAJ&oi=fnd&pg=PP1&dq=Baranov,+A.,+%26+Tournié,+E.+(Eds.).+(2013).+Semiconductor+Lasers:+Fundamentals+and+Applications.+Elsevier.&ots=M_G5Q2kVmM&sig=PtKCplj2v8i96mXS2u4EChoPR-0&redir_esc=y#v=onepage&q=Baranov%2C+A.%2C+%26+Tournié%2C+E.(Eds.).(2013).SemiconductorLasers%3AFundamentalsandApplications.)

- Elsevier.&f=false. [Accessed: 22-Sep-2019].
- [26] F. Monticone and A. Alu, "Metamaterial, plasmonic and nanophotonic devices," *Reports on Progress in Physics*. p. 036401, 2017.
- [27] J. Li, Y. Chen, and Y. Liu, "Mathematical simulation of metamaterial solar cells," *Adv. Appl. Math. Mech.*, vol. 3, no. 6, pp. 702–715, 2011.
- [28] P. Hamel *et al.*, "Spontaneous mirror-symmetry breaking in coupled photonic-crystal nanolasers," *Nat. Photonics*, vol. 9, no. 5, pp. 311–315, May 2015.
- [29] P. Lodahl *et al.*, "Controlling the dynamics of spontaneous emission from quantum dots by photonic crystals," *Nature*, vol. 430, no. 7000, pp. 654–657, Aug. 2004.
- [30] M. L. Juan, M. Righini, and R. Quidant, "Plasmon nano-optical tweezers," *Nature Photonics*, vol. 5, no. 6. pp. 349–356, Jun-2011.
- [31] M. Ohtsu, *Handbook of nano-optics and nanophotonics*. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2013.
- [32] M. Rang *et al.*, "Optical Near-Field Mapping of Plasmonic Nanoprisms," *Nano Lett.*, vol. 8, no. 10, pp. 3357–3363, Oct. 2008.
- [33] M. Ohtsu, K. Kobayashi, T. Kawazoe, S. Sangu, and T. Yatsui, "Nanophotonics: Design, fabrication, and operation of nanometric devices using optical near fields," *IEEE J. Sel. Top. Quantum Electron.*, vol. 8, no. 4, pp. 839–862, Jul. 2002.
- [34] Z. Yu, A. Raman, and S. Fan, "Nanophotonic light-trapping theory for solar cells," *Appl. Phys. A Mater. Sci. Process.*, vol. 105, no. 2, pp. 329–339, Nov. 2011.
- [35] K. X. Wang, Z. Yu, V. Liu, Y. Cui, and S. Fan, "Absorption enhancement in ultrathin crystalline silicon solar cells with antireflection and light-trapping nanocone gratings," *Nano Lett.*, vol. 12, no. 3, pp. 1616–1619, Mar. 2012.
- [36] M. Smeets *et al.*, "Prototyping of nanophotonic grating back contacts for light trapping in planar silicon solar cells," *Phys. Status Solidi Appl. Mater. Sci.*, vol. 213, no. 7, pp. 1949–1954, Jul. 2016.
- [37] C. Battaglia *et al.*, "Light trapping in solar cells: Can periodic beat random?," *ACS Nano*, vol. 6, no. 3, pp. 2790–2797, Mar. 2012.
- [38] A. Polman, M. Knight, E. C. Garnett, B. Ehrler, and W. C. Sinke, "Photovoltaic materials: Present efficiencies and future challenges," *Science*, vol. 352, no. 6283. American Association for the Advancement of Science, 15-Apr-2016.
- [39] K. R. Catchpole and A. Polman, "Plasmonic solar cells," *Opt. Express*, vol. 16, no. 26, p. 21793, Dec. 2008.
- [40] A. S. Shalin, C. R. Simovski, P. M. Voroshilov, and P. A. Belov, "Non-plasmonic light trapping for thin film solar cells," in *2014 8th International Congress on Advanced Electromagnetic Materials in Microwaves and Optics, METAMATERIALS 2014*, 2014, pp. 433–436.
- [41] J. Grandidier, D. M. Callahan, J. N. Munday, and H. A. Atwater, "Light absorption enhancement in thin-film solar cells using whispering gallery

- modes in dielectric nanospheres,” *Adv. Mater.*, vol. 23, no. 10, pp. 1272–1276, Mar. 2011.
- [42] S. E. Han and G. Chen, “Toward the lambertian limit of light trapping in thin nanostructured silicon solar cells,” *Nano Lett.*, vol. 10, no. 11, pp. 4692–4696, Nov. 2010.
- [43] A. V. Shah *et al.*, “Thin-film silicon solar cell technology,” *Prog. Photovoltaics Res. Appl.*, vol. 12, no. 23, pp. 113–142, Mar. 2004.
- [44] S. Mikulovic *et al.*, “On the photovoltaic effect in local field potential recordings,” *Neurophotonics*, vol. 3, no. 1, p. 015002, Jan. 2016.
- [45] S. Sharma, K. K. Jain, and A. Sharma, “Solar Cells: In Research and Applications—A Review,” *Mater. Sci. Appl.*, vol. 06, no. 12, pp. 1145–1155, 2015.
- [46] P. F. Ribeiro, B. K. Johnson, M. L. Crow, A. Arsoy, and Y. Liu, “Energy Storage systems for Advances Power Applications,” *Proc. IEEE*, vol. 89, no. 12, pp. 1744–1756, 2001.
- [47] S. Yamamoto, B. Young, B. Purwanto, F. Nakamasu, and T. Matsumoto, “Effect of solar radiation on the heat load of dairy heifers,” *Aust. J. Agric. Res.*, vol. 45, no. 8, p. 1741, 1994.
- [48] M. S. Safronova *et al.*, “Black-body radiation shifts and theoretical contributions to atomic clock research,” in *IEEE Transactions on Ultrasonics, Ferroelectrics, and Frequency Control*, 2010, vol. 57, no. 1, pp. 94–105.
- [49] S. Hodder and K. Parsons, “The effects of solar radiation and black body re-radiation on thermal comfort,” *Ergonomics*, vol. 51, no. 4, pp. 476–491, Apr. 2008.
- [50] C. Ferrari, A. Libbra, A. Muscio, and C. Siligardi, “Influence of the irradiance spectrum on solar reflectance measurements,” *Adv. Build. Energy Res.*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 244–253, 2013.
- [51] B. Marion, “Influence of atmospheric variations on photovoltaic performance and modeling their effects for days with clear skies,” in *Conference Record of the IEEE Photovoltaic Specialists Conference*, 2012, pp. 3402–3407.
- [52] A. L. Fahrenbruch and R. H. Bube, *Fundamentals of solar cells : photovoltaic solar energy conversion*. Academic Press, 1983.
- [53] M. A. Green, “Limiting photovoltaic efficiency under new ASTM International G173-based reference spectra,” *Prog. Photovoltaics Res. Appl.*, vol. 20, no. 8, pp. 954–959, Dec. 2012.
- [54] H. Cotal *et al.*, “III-V multijunction solar cells for concentrating photovoltaics,” *Energy and Environmental Science*, vol. 2, no. 2. pp. 174–192, 2009.
- [55] A. Luque, A. Martí, and C. Stanley, “Understanding intermediate-band solar cells,” *Nat. Photonics*, vol. 6, no. 3, pp. 146–152, Mar. 2012.
- [56] L. C. Hirst and N. J. Ekins-Daukes, “Fundamental losses in solar cells,” *Prog. Photovoltaics Res. Appl.*, vol. 19, no. 3, pp. 286–293, May 2011.
- [57] A. J. Heeger, “25th anniversary article: Bulk heterojunction solar cells:

- Understanding the mechanism of operation," *Advanced Materials*, vol. 26, no. 1. pp. 10–28, 08-Jan-2014.
- [58] U. Wurfel, A. Cuevas, and P. Wurfel, "Charge carrier separation in solar cells," *IEEE J. Photovoltaics*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 461–469, Jan. 2015.
- [59] D. J. Norris, A. L. Efros, and S. C. Erwin, "Doped nanocrystals," *Science*, vol. 319, no. 5871. pp. 1776–1779, 28-Mar-2008.
- [60] J. Liang, E. A. Schiff, S. Guha, B. Yan, and J. Yang, "Hole-mobility limit of amorphous silicon solar cells," *Applied Physics Letters*, vol. 88, no. 6. Feb-2006.
- [61] X. Zheng and L. Zhang, "Photonic nanostructures for solar energy conversion," *Energy and Environmental Science*, vol. 9, no. 8. Royal Society of Chemistry, pp. 2511–2532, 01-Aug-2016.
- [62] F. Feldmann, M. Simon, M. Bivour, C. Reichel, M. Hermle, and S. W. Glunz, "Carrier-selective contacts for Si solar cells," *Appl. Phys. Lett.*, vol. 104, no. 181105, pp. 1–4, 2014.
- [63] F. Feldmann, M. Simon, M. Bivour, C. Reichel, M. Hermle, and S. W. Glunz, "Efficient carrier-selective p- and n-contacts for Si solar cells," *Sol. Energy Mater. Sol. Cells*, vol. 131, pp. 100–104, 2014.
- [64] T. Soga, *Nanostructured materials for solar energy conversion*. Elsevier, 2006.
- [65] K. Yamamoto, M. Yoshimi, Y. Tawada, Y. Okamoto, A. Nakajima, and S. Igari, "Thin-film poly-Si solar cells on glass substrate fabricated at low temperature," *Appl. Phys. A Mater. Sci. Process.*, vol. 69, no. 2, pp. 179–185, Aug. 1999.
- [66] T. Kirchartz, B. E. Pieters, J. Kirkpatrick, U. Rau, and J. Nelson, "Recombination via tail states in polythiophene:fullerene solar cells," *Phys. Rev. B - Condens. Matter Mater. Phys.*, vol. 83, no. 11, Mar. 2011.
- [67] T. Titze *et al.*, "Transport in Nanoporous Materials Including MOFs: The Applicability of Fick's Laws," *Angew. Chemie - Int. Ed.*, vol. 54, no. 48, pp. 14580–14583, Nov. 2015.
- [68] D. R. Poirier, G. H. Geiger, D. R. Poirier, and G. H. Geiger, "Fick's Law and Diffusivity of Materials," in *Transport Phenomena in Materials Processing*, Springer International Publishing, 2016, pp. 419–461.
- [69] S. W. Webb and K. Pruess, "The use of Fick's law for modeling trace gas diffusion in porous media," *Transp. Porous Media*, vol. 51, no. 3, pp. 327–341, Jun. 2003.
- [70] C. M. Hsieh, P. C. Murley, and R. R. O'Brien, "A Field-funneling Effect on the Collection of Alpha-Particle-Generated Carriers in Silicon Devices," *IEEE Electron Device Lett.*, vol. 2, no. 4, pp. 103–105, 1981.
- [71] M. J. Kerr and A. Cuevas, "General parameterization of Auger recombination in crystalline silicon," *J. Appl. Phys.*, vol. 91, no. 3, pp. 2473–2480, Feb. 2002.
- [72] Y. C. Shen, G. O. Mueller, S. Watanabe, N. F. Gardner, A. Munkholm, and M. R. Krames, "Auger recombination in InGaN measured by photoluminescence," *Appl. Phys. Lett.*, vol. 91, no. 14, 2007.

- [73] Y. Yang *et al.*, “Low surface recombination velocity in solution-grown CH₃NH₃PbBr₃ perovskite single crystal,” *Nat. Commun.*, vol. 6, Aug. 2015.
- [74] H. C. Sio, S. P. Phang, T. Trupke, and D. MacDonald, “Impact of Phosphorous Gettering and Hydrogenation on the Surface Recombination Velocity of Grain Boundaries in p-Type Multicrystalline Silicon,” *IEEE J. Photovoltaics*, vol. 5, no. 5, pp. 1357–1365, Sep. 2015.
- [75] P. Spinelli, B. W. H. Van De Loo, A. H. G. Vlooswijk, W. M. M. Kessels, and I. Cesar, “Quantification of pn-Junction Recombination in Interdigitated Back-Contact Crystalline Silicon Solar Cells,” *IEEE J. Photovoltaics*, vol. 7, no. 5, pp. 1176–1183, Sep. 2017.
- [76] P. H. Bueno, D. F. Costa, A. Eick, A. Carvalho, and D. W. L. Monteiro, “The behavior of series resistance of a p-n junction: the diode and the solar cell cases,” in *Physics, Simulation, and Photonic Engineering of Photovoltaic Devices V*, 2016, vol. 9743, p. 97431F.
- [77] S. Wang, X. Yan, X. Zhang, J. Li, and X. Ren, “Axially connected nanowire core-shell p-n junctions: a composite structure for high-efficiency solar cells,” *Nanoscale Res. Lett.*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 1–7, 2015.
- [78] O. Almora, I. Zarazua, E. Mas-Marza, I. Mora-Sero, J. Bisquert, and G. Garcia-Belmonte, “Capacitive dark currents, hysteresis, and electrode polarization in lead halide perovskite solar cells,” *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.*, vol. 6, no. 9, pp. 1645–1652, May 2015.
- [79] Z. Pei, S. T. Chang, C. W. Liu, and Y. C. Chen, “Numerical simulation on the photovoltaic behavior of an amorphous-silicon nanowire-array solar cell,” *IEEE Electron Device Lett.*, vol. 30, no. 12, pp. 1305–1307, Dec. 2009.
- [80] S. M. Willis, C. Cheng, H. E. Assender, and A. A. R. Watt, “The transitional heterojunction behavior of PbS/ZnO colloidal quantum dot solar cells,” *Nano Lett.*, vol. 12, no. 3, pp. 1522–1526, Mar. 2012.
- [81] B. Subudhi and R. Pradhan, “A comparative study on maximum power point tracking techniques for photovoltaic power systems,” *IEEE Trans. Sustain. Energy*, vol. 4, no. 1, pp. 89–98, 2013.
- [82] T. Esmar and P. L. Chapman, “Comparison of photovoltaic array maximum power point tracking techniques,” *IEEE Trans. Energy Convers.*, vol. 22, no. 2, pp. 439–449, Jun. 2007.
- [83] N. C. Giebink, G. P. Wiederrecht, M. R. Wasielewski, and S. R. Forrest, “Ideal diode equation for organic heterojunctions. I. Derivation and application,” *Phys. Rev. B*, vol. 82, no. 15, Oct. 2010.
- [84] I. Tobías and A. Luque, “Ideal efficiency of monolithic, series-connected multijunction solar cells,” *Prog. Photovoltaics Res. Appl.*, vol. 10, no. 5, pp. 323–329, Aug. 2002.
- [85] B. Michl, D. Impera, M. Bivour, W. Warta, and M. C. Schubert, “Suns-PLI as a powerful tool for spatially resolved fill factor analysis of solar cells,” *Prog. Photovoltaics Res. Appl.*, vol. 22, no. 5, pp. 581–586, May 2014.
- [86] S. Yoo, B. Domercq, S. R. Marder, N. R. Armstrong, and B. Kippelen,

- “Modeling of organic photovoltaic cells with large fill factor and high efficiency,” in *Organic Photovoltaics V*, 2004, vol. 5520, p. 110.
- [87] J. Haschke *et al.*, “Interdigitated back-contacted silicon heterojunction solar cells with improved fill factor and efficiency,” *IEEE J. Photovoltaics*, vol. 1, no. 2, pp. 130–134, 2011.
- [88] D. Hinken, K. Ramspeck, K. Bothe, B. Fischer, and R. Brendel, “Series resistance imaging of solar cells by voltage dependent electroluminescence,” *Appl. Phys. Lett.*, vol. 91, no. 18, 2007.
- [89] A. Ortiz-Conde, D. Lugo-Muñoz, and F. J. García-Sánchez, “An explicit multiexponential model as an alternative to traditional solar cell models with series and shunt resistances,” *IEEE J. Photovoltaics*, vol. 2, no. 3, pp. 261–268, 2012.
- [90] A. Ortiz-Conde and F. J. García Sánchez, “Approximate analytical expression for equation of ideal diode with series and shunt resistances,” *Electron. Lett.*, vol. 28, no. 21, pp. 1964–1965, 1992.
- [91] S. Hou, “Overview of Solar Photovoltaic Technology,” 2017, pp. 1–30.
- [92] N. D. Kaushika, A. Mishra, A. K. Rai, N. D. Kaushika, A. Mishra, and A. K. Rai, “High Performance Solar Cells,” in *Solar Photovoltaics*, Springer International Publishing, 2018, pp. 139–142.
- [93] A. J. Moulé and K. Meerholz, “Minimizing optical losses in bulk heterojunction polymer solar cells,” *Appl. Phys. B Lasers Opt.*, vol. 86, no. 4, pp. 721–727, Mar. 2007.
- [94] G. R. Walker and P. C. Sernia, “Cascaded DC-DC converter connection of photovoltaic modules,” in *2002 IEEE 33rd Annual IEEE Power Electronics Specialists Conference. Proceedings (Cat. No.02CH37289)*, vol. 1, pp. 24–29.
- [95] H. Sai, Y. Kanamori, K. Arafune, Y. Ohshita, and M. Yamaguchi, “Light trapping effect of submicron surface textures in crystalline Si solar cells,” *Prog. Photovoltaics Res. Appl.*, vol. 15, no. 5, pp. 415–423, Aug. 2007.
- [96] S. S. Hegedus and W. N. Shafarman, “Thin-film solar cells: device measurements and analysis,” *Prog. Photovoltaics Res. Appl.*, vol. 12, no. 23, pp. 155–176, Mar. 2004.
- [97] V. E. Ferry *et al.*, “Light trapping in ultrathin plasmonic solar cells,” *Opt. Express*, vol. 18, no. S2, p. A237, Jun. 2010.
- [98] C. Battaglia *et al.*, “Nanomoulding of transparent zinc oxide electrodes for efficient light trapping in solar cells,” *Nat. Photonics*, vol. 5, no. 9, pp. 535–538, Sep. 2011.
- [99] M. Boccard *et al.*, “Optimization of ZnO front electrodes for high-efficiency micromorph thin-film Si solar cells,” *IEEE J. Photovoltaics*, vol. 2, no. 3, pp. 229–235, 2012.
- [100] S. Fahr, T. Kirchartz, C. Rockstuhl, and F. Lederer, “Approaching the Lambertian limit in randomly textured thin-film solar cells,” *Opt. Express*, vol. 19, no. S4, p. A865, Jul. 2011.
- [101] J. Zhao, A. Wang, P. Altermatt, and M. A. Green, “Twenty-four percent

- efficient silicon solar cells with double layer antireflection coatings and reduced resistance loss," *Appl. Phys. Lett.*, p. 3636, 1995.
- [102] M. A. Green, A. W. Blakers, J. Zhao, A. M. Milne, A. Wang, and X. Dai, "Characterization of 23-Percent Efficient Silicon Solar Cells," *IEEE Trans. Electron Devices*, vol. 37, no. 2, pp. 331–336, 1990.
- [103] S. Dauwe, L. Mittelstädt, A. Metz, and R. Hezel, "Experimental evidence of parasitic shunting in silicon nitride rear surface passivated solar cells," *Prog. Photovoltaics Res. Appl.*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 271–278, Jun. 2002.
- [104] H. Denio, "Aerial solar Thermography and condition monitoring of photovoltaic systems," in *Conference Record of the IEEE Photovoltaic Specialists Conference, 2012*, pp. 613–618.
- [105] A. Taşcıoğlu, O. Taşkin, and A. Vardar, "A Power Case Study for Monocrystalline and Polycrystalline Solar Panels in Bursa City, Turkey," *Int. J. Photoenergy*, vol. 2016, 2016.
- [106] M. Stupca, M. Alsalhi, T. Al Saud, A. Almuhanha, and M. H. Nayfeh, "Enhancement of polycrystalline silicon solar cells using ultrathin films of silicon nanoparticle," *Appl. Phys. Lett.*, vol. 91, no. 6, 2007.
- [107] I. Gordon, L. Carnel, D. Van Gestel, G. Beaucarne, and J. Poortmans, "8% Efficient thin-film polycrystalline-silicon solar cells based on aluminum-induced crystallization and thermal CVD," *Prog. Photovoltaics Res. Appl.*, vol. 15, no. 7, pp. 575–586, Nov. 2007.
- [108] C. H. Seager, D. S. Ginley, and J. D. Zook, "Improvement of polycrystalline silicon solar cells with grain-boundary hydrogenation techniques," *Appl. Phys. Lett.*, vol. 36, no. 10, pp. 831–833, 1980.
- [109] R. E. I. Schropp, R. Carius, and G. Beaucarne, "Amorphous silicon, microcrystalline silicon, and thin-film polycrystalline silicon solar cells," *MRS Bull.*, vol. 32, no. 3, pp. 219–224, 2007.
- [110] W. Wang *et al.*, "Device characteristics of CZTSSe thin-film solar cells with 12.6% efficiency," *Adv. Energy Mater.*, vol. 4, no. 7, May 2014.
- [111] R. A. Pala, J. White, E. Barnard, J. Liu, and M. L. Brongersma, "Design of plasmonic thin-film solar cells with broadband absorption enhancements," *Adv. Mater.*, vol. 21, no. 34, pp. 3504–3509, Sep. 2009.
- [112] P. Bermel, C. Luo, L. Zeng, L. C. Kimerling, and J. D. Joannopoulos, "Improving thin-film crystalline silicon solar cell efficiencies with photonic crystals," *Opt. Express*, vol. 15, no. 25, p. 16986, 2007.
- [113] A. J. Nozik, M. C. Beard, J. M. Luther, M. Law, R. J. Ellingson, and J. C. Johnson, "Semiconductor quantum dots and quantum dot arrays and applications of multiple exciton generation to third-generation photovoltaic solar cells," *Chem. Rev.*, vol. 110, no. 11, pp. 6873–6890, Nov. 2010.
- [114] A. Fujishima and X. T. Zhang, "Solid-State Dye-Sensitized Solar Cells," in *Nanostructured Materials for Solar Energy Conversion*, Elsevier, 2006, pp. 255–273.
- [115] B. E. Hardin, H. J. Snaith, and M. D. McGehee, "The renaissance of dye-

- sensitized solar cells," *Nature Photonics*, vol. 6, no. 3. pp. 162–169, Mar-2012.
- [116] A. Du Pasquier, H. Chen, and Y. Lu, "Dye sensitized solar cells using well-aligned zinc oxide nanotip arrays," *Appl. Phys. Lett.*, vol. 89, no. 25, 2006.
- [117] I. Chung, B. Lee, J. He, R. P. H. Chang, and M. G. Kanatzidis, "All-solid-state dye-sensitized solar cells with high efficiency," *Nature*, vol. 485, no. 7399, pp. 486–489, May 2012.
- [118] A. Nakasa, H. Usami, S. Sumikura, S. Hasegawa, T. Koyama, and E. Suzuki, "A high voltage dye-sensitized solar cell using a nanoporous NiO photocathode," *Chem. Lett.*, vol. 34, no. 4, pp. 500–501, Apr. 2005.
- [119] L. M. Goncalves, V. De Zea Bermudez, H. A. Ribeiro, and A. M. Mendes, "Dye-sensitized solar cells: A safe bet for the future," *Energy Environ. Sci.*, vol. 1, no. 6, pp. 655–667, 2008.
- [120] D. Y. Son *et al.*, "Self-formed grain boundary healing layer for highly efficient CH₃ NH₃ PbI₃ perovskite solar cells," *Nat. Energy*, vol. 1, no. 7, Jul. 2016.
- [121] X. Zheng *et al.*, "Defect passivation in hybrid perovskite solar cells using quaternary ammonium halide anions and cations," *Nat. Energy*, vol. 2, no. 7, Jul. 2017.
- [122] J. Müller, B. Rech, J. Springer, and M. Vanecek, "TCO and light trapping in silicon thin film solar cells," *Sol. Energy*, vol. 77, no. 6, pp. 917–930, Dec. 2004.
- [123] J. A. Anna Selvan, A. E. Delahoy, S. Guo, and Y. M. Li, "A new light trapping TCO for nc-Si:H solar cells," *Sol. Energy Mater. Sol. Cells*, vol. 90, no. 18–19, pp. 3371–3376, Nov. 2006.
- [124] K. Ernst, A. Belaidi, and R. Könenkamp, "Solar cell with extremely thin absorber on highly structured substrate," *Semicond. Sci. Technol.*, vol. 18, no. 6, pp. 475–479, Jun. 2003.
- [125] J. M. Luther, P. K. Jain, T. Ewers, and A. P. Alivisatos, "Localized surface plasmon resonances arising from free carriers in doped quantum dots," *Nat. Mater.*, vol. 10, no. 5, pp. 361–366, 2011.
- [126] D. Estrada-Wiese, E. A. Del Río-Chanona, and J. A. Del Río, "Stochastic optimization of broadband reflecting photonic structures," *Sci. Rep.*, vol. 8, no. 1, Dec. 2018.
- [127] C. Chen *et al.*, "Dual functional asymmetric plasmonic structures for solar water purification and pollution detection," *Nano Energy*, vol. 51, pp. 451–456, Sep. 2018.
- [128] X. Qin, Y. Wu, Z. Xia, J. Zhou, and Z. Zhang, "Beneficial effect of reducing symmetry on the enhancement of optical absorption of nanohole arrays," *Opt. Commun.*, vol. 427, pp. 90–94, Nov. 2018.
- [129] O. Isabella, R. Vismara, D. N. P. Linssen, K. X. Wang, S. Fan, and M. Zeman, "Advanced light trapping scheme in decoupled front and rear textured thin-film silicon solar cells," *Sol. Energy*, vol. 162, pp. 344–356, Mar. 2018.
- [130] N. Zin *et al.*, "Polyimide for silicon solar cells with double-sided textured

- pyramids," *Sol. Energy Mater. Sol. Cells*, vol. 183, pp. 200–204, Aug. 2018.
- [131] F. M. H. Korany, M. F. O. Hameed, M. Hussein, R. Mubarak, M. I. Eladawy, and S. S. A. Obayya, "Conical structures for highly efficient solar cell applications," *J. Nanophotonics*, vol. 12, no. 01, p. 1, Mar. 2018.
- [132] M. Hussein, N. F. F. Areed, M. F. O. Hameed, and S. S. A. Obayya, "Hybrid core semiconductor nanowires for solar cell applications," in *Proceedings of the International Conference on Numerical Simulation of Optoelectronic Devices, NUSOD, 2014*, pp. 89–90.
- [133] H. J. Seok, J. K. Kim, and H. K. Kim, "Effective passivation of Ag nanowire network by transparent tetrahedral amorphous carbon film for flexible and transparent thin film heaters," *Sci. Rep.*, vol. 8, no. 1, Dec. 2018.
- [134] J. Holmér *et al.*, "An STM – SEM setup for characterizing photon and electron induced effects in single photovoltaic nanowires," *Nano Energy*, vol. 53, pp. 175–181, Nov. 2018.
- [135] S. Lee *et al.*, "Robust nanoscale contact of silver nanowire electrodes to semiconductors to achieve high performance chalcogenide thin film solar cells," *Nano Energy*, vol. 53, pp. 675–682, Nov. 2018.
- [136] M. Hussein, K. R. Mahmoud, M. F. O. Hameed, and S. S. A. Obayya, "Optimal design of vertical silicon nanowires solar cell using hybrid optimization algorithm," *J. Photonics Energy*, vol. 8, no. 02, p. 1, Nov. 2017.
- [137] G. Barbillon, Ed., *Nanoplasmonics - Fundamentals and Applications*. InTech, 2017.
- [138] P. Spinelli *et al.*, "Plasmonic light trapping in thin-film Si solar cells," *Journal of Optics*, vol. 14, no. 2, Feb-2012.
- [139] A. N. Sprafke and R. B. Wehrspohn, "Light trapping concepts for photon management in solar cells," *Green*, vol. 2, no. 4. Walter de Gruyter GmbH, pp. 177–187, 2012.
- [140] A. P. Vasudev, J. A. Schuller, and M. L. Brongersma, "Nanophotonic light trapping with patterned transparent conductive oxides," *Opt. Express*, vol. 20, no. S3, p. A385, May 2012.
- [141] M. Bauerly and Y. Liu, "Computational modeling and experimental investigation of effects of compositional elements on interface and design aesthetics," *Int. J. Hum. Comput. Stud.*, vol. 64, no. 8, pp. 670–682, Aug. 2006.
- [142] R. E. Levitt, "Computational Modeling of Organizations Comes of Age," *Comput. Math. Organ. Theory*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 127–145, Aug. 2004.
- [143] M. Kirca, A. Gül, E. Ekinçi, F. Yardim, and A. Mugan, "Computational modeling of micro-cellular carbon foams," *Finite Elem. Anal. Des.*, vol. 44, no. 1–2, pp. 45–52, Dec. 2007.
- [144] D. A. Beard, J. B. Bassingthwaighte, and A. S. Greene, "Computational modeling of physiological systems," *Physiological Genomics*, vol. 23, no. 1, pp. 1–3, 21-Sep-2005.
- [145] T. Rylander, P. Ingelström, and A. Bondeson, "The Finite-Difference Time-Domain Method," 2013, pp. 63–92.

- [146] T. Namiki, "A New FDTD algorithm based on alternating-Direction implicit method," *IEEE Trans. Microw. Theory Tech.*, vol. 47, no. 10, pp. 2003–2007, Oct. 1999.
- [147] O. Chadebec, J. L. Coulomb, and F. Janet, "A review of magnetostatic moment method," in *IEEE Transactions on Magnetics*, 2006, vol. 42, no. 4, pp. 515–520.
- [148] C. B. Tan, S. H. Yeo, and A. Khoh, "Modeling of wafer alignment marks using geometrical theory of diffraction (GTD)," in *Metrology, Inspection, and Process Control for Microlithography XIX*, 2005, vol. 5752, p. 977.
- [149] Ł. Kulas and M. Mrozowski, "Reduced order models of refined Yee's cells," *IEEE Microw. Wirel. Components Lett.*, vol. 13, no. 4, pp. 164–166, Apr. 2003.
- [150] R. W. Ziolkowski and E. Heyman, "Wave propagation in media having negative permittivity and permeability," *Phys. Rev. E - Stat. Physics, Plasmas, Fluids, Relat. Interdiscip. Top.*, vol. 64, no. 5, p. 15, 2001.
- [151] K. J. Willis, S. C. Hagness, and I. Knezevic, "Terahertz conductivity of doped silicon calculated using the ensemble Monte Carlo/finite-difference time-domain simulation technique," *Appl. Phys. Lett.*, vol. 96, no. 6, 2010.
- [152] D. Li and C. D. Sarris, "FDTD lattice termination with periodic boundary conditions," in *IEEE MTT-S International Microwave Symposium Digest*, 2009, pp. 329–332.
- [153] A. Lavrinenko *et al.*, "Comprehensive FDTD modelling of photonic crystal waveguide components," *Opt. Express*, vol. 12, no. 2, p. 234, 2004.
- [154] M. Farzarian, F. Arbabi, and R. Pak, "PML solution of longitudinal wave propagation in heterogeneous media," *Earthq. Eng. Eng. Vib.*, vol. 15, no. 2, pp. 357–368, Jun. 2016.
- [155] D. M. Sullivan, *Electromagnetic simulation using the FDTD method*. Wiley, 2013.
- [156] S. Yang, Z. Chen, Y. Yu, and S. Ponomarenko, "On the divergence properties of the new efficiency-improved divergence preserved ADI-FDTD method," in *IEEE MTT-S International Microwave Symposium Digest*, 2013.
- [157] K. Yasumoto, *Electromagnetic theory and applications for photonic crystals*. Taylor & Francis, 2006.
- [158] K. Naishadham, "Stability considerations in the application of PML absorbing boundary condition to FDTD simulation of microwave circuits," in *1996 IEEE MTT-S International Microwave Symposium Digest*, vol. 2, pp. 581–584.
- [159] D. M. Callahan, K. A. W. Horowitz, and H. A. Atwater, "Light trapping in ultrathin silicon photonic crystal superlattices with randomly-textured dielectric incouplers," *Opt. Express*, vol. 21, no. 25, p. 30315, Dec. 2013.
- [160] A. H. K. Mahmoud, M. Hussein, M. F. O. Hameed, M. Abdel-Aziz, H. M. Hosny, and S. S. A. Obayya, "Optoelectronic performance of a modified nanopyramid solar cell," *J. Opt. Soc. Am. B*, vol. 36, no. 2, p. 357, Feb. 2019.
- [161] L. Angermann and S. Wang, "Three-dimensional exponentially fitted conforming tetrahedral finite elements for the semiconductor continuity

- equations," *Appl. Numer. Math.*, vol. 46, no. 1, pp. 19–43, 2003.
- [162] G. Y. Abdel-Latif, M. F. O. Hameed, M. Hussein, M. Abdel Razzak, and S. S. A. Obayya, "Characteristics of highly efficient star-shaped nanowires solar cell," *J. Photonics Energy*, vol. 8, no. 04, p. 1, Oct. 2018.
- [163] J. L. Cruz-Campa *et al.*, "Microsystems enabled photovoltaics: 14.9% efficient 14 μm thick crystalline silicon solar cell," *Sol. Energy Mater. Sol. Cells*, vol. 95, no. 2, pp. 551–558, Feb. 2011.
- [164] J. Yoon *et al.*, "Flexible concentrator photovoltaics based on microscale silicon solar cells embedded in luminescent waveguides," *Nat. Commun.*, vol. 2, no. 1, 2011.
- [165] G. Li, H. Li, J. Y. L. Ho, M. Wong, and H. S. Kwok, "Nanopyramid structure for ultrathin c-Si tandem solar cells," *Nano Lett.*, vol. 14, no. 5, pp. 2563–2568, May 2014.
- [166] R. Yu, Q. Lin, S. F. Leung, and Z. Fan, "Nanomaterials and nanostructures for efficient light absorption and photovoltaics," *Nano Energy*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 57–72, Jan-2012.
- [167] J. Zhu *et al.*, "Optical absorption enhancement in amorphous silicon nanowire and nanocone arrays," *Nano Lett.*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 279–282, Jan. 2009.
- [168] M. Hussein, M. F. O. Hameed, N. F. F. Areed, A. Yahia, and S. S. A. Obayya, "Funnel-shaped silicon nanowire for highly efficient light trapping," *Opt. Lett.*, vol. 41, no. 5, p. 1010, Mar. 2016.
- [169] Ghada Yassin Abdel-Latif; Mohamed Farhat O. Hameed; Mohamed Hussein; Maher Abdel Razzak; Salah S. A. Obayya, "Electrical characteristics of funnel-shaped silicon nanowire solar cells," *J. Photonics Energy*, vol. 7, no. 04, p. 1, Dec. 2017.
- [170] Y. Q. Zhao *et al.*, "Silicon nanohole photovoltaic cells," in *Conference Record of the IEEE Photovoltaic Specialists Conference, 2011*, pp. 000699–000702.
- [171] C. M. Hsu, S. T. Connor, M. X. Tang, and Y. Cui, "Wafer-scale silicon nanopillars and nanocones by Langmuir-Blodgett assembly and etching," *Appl. Phys. Lett.*, vol. 93, no. 13, 2008.
- [172] C. Zhang, X. Li, A. Shang, S. Wu, Y. Zhan, and Z. Yang, "Design of dual-diameter nanoholes for efficient solar-light harvesting," *Nanoscale Res. Lett.*, vol. 9, no. 1, 2014.
- [173] Y. Shi, X. Wang, W. Liu, T. Yang, J. Ma, and F. Yang, "Nanopyramids and rear-located Ag nanoparticles for broad spectrum absorption enhancement in thin-film solar cells," *Opt. Express*, vol. 22, no. 17, p. 20473, Aug. 2014.
- [174] Z. Jia, Q. Cheng, J. Song, M. Si, and Z. Luo, "Optical properties of a grating-nanorod assembly structure for solar cells," *Opt. Commun.*, vol. 376, pp. 14–20, Oct. 2016.
- [175] S. Zhang *et al.*, "High-efficiency photon capturing in ultrathin silicon solar cells with double-sided skewed nanopyramid arrays," *J. Opt. (United Kingdom)*, vol. 19, no. 10, Sep. 2017.

- [176] X. Meng, E. Drouard, G. Gomard, R. Peretti, A. Fave, and C. Seassal, "Combined front and back diffraction gratings for broad band light trapping in thin film solar cell," *Opt. Express*, vol. 20, no. S5, p. A560, Sep. 2012.
- [177] X. Fang, C. Y. Zhao, and H. Bao, "Radiative behaviors of crystalline silicon nanowire and nanohole arrays for photovoltaic applications," *J. Quant. Spectrosc. Radiat. Transf.*, vol. 133, pp. 579–588, Jan. 2014.
- [178] S. S. A. Obayya, M. Hussein, M. F. O. Hameed, and A. Mahmoud, "Characteristics of modified nanopyramid silicon solar cell," 2019, p. 52.
- [179] S. M. Mahpeykar, Q. Xiong, and X. Wang, "Resonance-induced absorption enhancement in colloidal quantum dot solar cells using nanostructured electrodes," *Opt. Express*, vol. 22, no. S6, p. A1576, Oct. 2014.
- [180] G. Zheng, W. Zhang, L. Xu, Y. Chen, and Y. Liu, "Absorbance enhancement of thin film solar cells with front double dielectric and back metallic grating," *Infrared Phys. Technol.*, vol. 67, pp. 52–57, 2014.
- [181] Z. Jia, Q. Cheng, J. Song, Y. Zhou, and Y. Liu, "Enhanced absorptance of the assembly structure incorporating germanium nanorods and two-dimensional silicon gratings for photovoltaics," *Appl. Opt.*, vol. 55, no. 31, p. 8821, Nov. 2016.
- [182] A. Kirkeminde *et al.*, "Surface-passivated plasmonic nano-pyramids for bulk heterojunction solar cell photocurrent enhancement," *Nanoscale*, vol. 4, no. 15, pp. 4421–4425, Aug. 2012.
- [183] D. A. Goldman, J. Murray, and J. N. Munday, "Nanophotonic resonators for InP solar cells," *Opt. Express*, vol. 24, no. 10, p. A925, May 2016.
- [184] Z. Li, Y. C. Wenas, L. Fu, S. Mokkaapati, H. H. Tan, and C. Jagadish, "Influence of Electrical Design on Core - Shell GaAs Nanowire Array Solar Cells," *IEEE J. Photovoltaics*, vol. 5, no. 3, pp. 854–864, May 2015.
- [185] X. Yan, C. Zhang, J. Wang, X. Zhang, and X. Ren, "A High-Efficiency Si Nanowire Array/Perovskite Hybrid Solar Cell," *Nanoscale Res. Lett.*, vol. 12, no. 1, Dec. 2017.
- [186] P. Wang *et al.*, "Periodic Upright Nanopyramids for Light Management Applications in Ultrathin Crystalline Silicon Solar Cells," *IEEE J. Photovoltaics*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 493–501, Mar. 2017.

في هذه الأطروحة ، يتم تقديم وتحليل الخصائص البصرية والكهربائية للخلايا الشمسية السيليكون المعدلة ذات الهرم السطحى و تتكون الخلايا الشمسية الشبكية المعدلة من هرم نانومتري على سطح الخلية لزياده مسار الشعاع الضوئى علوي جزىء مستطيلى نانو سفلية. يتم ضبط الابعاد الهندسية للتصميم المقترح لتعظيم الامتصاص البصري وتحسين الكفاءة القصوى. يتم استخدام طريقه الفروق المحدود ذات الاتجاهيه الكامله عبر حزم البرامج العدديه لدراسة أداء الإلكترونيات الضوئية للتصميم المقترح. في هذا الاستقصاء ، يتم حساب كثافة تيار الدائرة القصيرة (J_{sc}) ، معدل التوليد البصري ، جهد الدائرة المفتوحة (V_{oc}) ، عامل التعبئة الكهربائية ، وكفاءة تحويل الطاقة الكهربائية (PCE) بالكامل. علاوة على ذلك ، يتم أيضاً دراسة تأثيرات تركيز نسبه الشوائب وعمر الناقل على أداء الجهاز. يوفر التصميم المعدل كفاءة بصرية قصوى تبلغ 40.93% و كثافة تيار بصري 33.49 مللي أمبير / سم² ، على التوالي ، مع تحسن بنسبة 28.3% على هرم نانو التقليدي. هذا التحسين يرجع إلى قدرة الجدران الجانبية المشبكة على احتجاز مزيد من الضوء عبر الطبقة النشطة. بالإضافة إلى ذلك ، يمكن أن يظهر التباعد بين هياكل هرم نانو المجاورة رنيناً ، مما يساهم في تحسين امتصاص النطاق العريض. يعرض التصميم المقترح جهد الدائرة المفتوحة 0.57 فولت ، 28.42 مللي أمبير / سم² ، وكفاءة تحويل الطاقة الكهربائية بنسبة 13.3 % ، وهي أفضل من جهد الدائرة المفتوحة من 0.559 فولت ، كثافة تيار 19.6 مللي أمبير / سم² ، وكفاءة تحويل الطاقة الكهربائية من 8.95% من هرم نانو تقليدي

ملخص

تعتبر أحد أكثر اهتمامات العالم مواجهة الاستهلاك العالمي للطاقة نظراً لتزايد السكان. ويعتقد أن موارد الوقود الأحفوري هي المصدر الرئيسي للطاقة في جميع أنحاء العالم حالياً ، و لذلك يعتبر إنشاء مصادر الطاقة المتجددة وفيرة الطبيعية كبديل عن الوقود الأحفوري التقليدي هو موضوع البحث. و تعتبر الطاقه الشمسيه أحد مصادر الطاقة المتجددة الرئيسية التي تزيد بمقدار عشره الاف مرة عن الطاقة المستهلكة.

يمكن تحويل الإشعاع الشمسي مباشرة إلى طاقة كهربائية عبر الخلايا الكهروضوئية. في الوقت الحاضر ، تشكل الخلايا الشمسية المصنوعة من السيليكون حوالي 90% من سوق الطاقة الكهروضوئية بسبب عدم سميتها ، وفرة السيلكون في قشرة الأرض والاستقرار طويل الأجل. على الرغم من ذلك ، فإن الحصول على امتصاص كامل للطيف الشمسي بأكمله يحتاج إلى كميات كبيرة من مادة السيليكون مما يزيد من تكلفة المنتج في النهاية. تعتبر الخلايا الشمسية ذات الأغشية الرقيقة التي يبلغ سمكها بضعة ميكرومتر طريقة بديلة مفيدة لتقليل كمية المواد وميزانية التصنيع. لسوء الحظ ، فإن الامتصاص المنخفض للخلايا الشمسية الدقيقة يجعلها أقل كفاءة. في هذا الصدد ، تعد تقنيات محاصرة الضوء خلال المادة النشطة للخلايا الشمسية تقنيه واعدة لتحسين أداء الخلايا الشمسية الرقيقة للفيلم. يمكن تحقيق ذلك عن طريق زيادة طول المسار البصري داخل طبقة الامتصاص. وقد تم استخدام العديد من التقنيات مثل الهياكل البلازمية والبلورات الضوئية والشبكة الدورية والأسلاك النانوية لتطوير كفاءة الخلايا الشمسية. ومع ذلك ، فإن بعض هذه التقنيات مثل هياكل النسيج الدورية أو العشوائية يمكن أن تسبب عيوباً وأضراراً تؤثر على الخلية الشمسية. أداء. علاوة على ذلك ، هناك حاجة إلى مكونات باهظة الثمن وتقنيات معقدة مثل الطباعة الحجرية والحفر لتصنيع هذه الهياكل التي تزيد من تكلفة الوحدة النهائية. إن تصميم الخلايا الشمسية عالية الطاقة مع استهلاك منخفض للمواد وتكلفة تصنيع أقل هو الحل النهائي لهذه المشكلات. خلايا السيليكون الشمسية الملمس هي طريقة بديلة جيدة للخلايا الشمسية ذات الأغشية الرقيقة. تتمتع الخلايا الشمسية المصنوعة من السيليكون الملمس بمزايا تركيز الضوء دون أي أنظمة تتبع ، ومحاصرة للضوء مع عامل تحسين لطول المسار البصري ، وإنتاج منخفض التكلفة ، وعالية الأداء.

جامعة عين شمس
كلية العلوم
قسم الفيزياء

صفحة الشكر

اشكر الساده الاساتذه الذين قاموا بالاشراف و هم

1. د. هاله محمد حسني (رحمها الله)
استاذ مساعد متفرغ بقسم الفيزياء- كلية العلوم – جامعة عين شمس
2. د. محمد حسن عبد العزيز
استاذ مساعد بقسم العلوم الأساسية- كلية الحاسبات والمعلومات – جامعة عين شمس
3. د. محمد فرحات عثمان
استاذ مساعد بقسم الرياضيات الفيزياء الهندسيه- كلية الهندسة – جامعة المنصورة

ثم الاشخاص الذين تعاونوا معي بالبحث و هم

1. د. محمد حسين عبد الرازق
مدرس بقسم الفيزياء - كلية العلوم - جامعة عين شمس
2. أ.د صلاح صبرى احمد عبيه
مدير مركز الفوتونات والمواد الذكية - مدينة زويل للعلوم والتكنولوجيا
3. أ.د. حسن حسن رمضان
استاذ دكتور متفرغ بقسم العلوم الاساسيه بكلية الحاسبات والمعلومات - جامعه عين شمس

و كذلك الهيئات الاتيه

- قسم العلوم الأساسية كلية علوم الحاسب والمعلومات
- قسم الفيزياء كلية العلوم جامعة عين شمس
- مركز الفوتونات و مواد الذكيه بمدينة زويل للعلوم و التكنولوجيه

جامعة عين شمس
كلية العلوم
قسم الفيزياء

صفحة الموافقه

الاسم: عمرو هشام خلف محمود

عنوان الرسالة: التوصيف البصري لخلايا شمسية عالية الكفاءة ذات البنية النانومترية
الدرجة العلمية: ماجستير فى علوم الفيزياء (فيزياء البصريات)

اعضاء لجنه الاشراف:

1. المرحومة د. هاله محمد حسني
الوظيفة/ استاذ مساعد متفرغ بقسم الفيزياء - كلية العلوم جامعة عين شمس
التوقيع/.....
2. د. محمد حسن عبد العزيز
الوظيفة/ استاذ مساعد بقسم العلوم الأساسية- كلية الحاسبات والمعلومات - جامعة عين شمس
التوقيع/.....
3. د. محمد فرحات عثمان
الوظيفة/ استاذ مساعد بقسم الرياضيات و الفيزياء الهندسيه - كلية الهندسة - جامعة المنصورة
التوقيع/.....

اعضاء لجنه التحكيم:

1. د. محمد حسن عبد العزيز
الوظيفة/ استاذ مساعد بقسم العلوم الأساسية- كلية الحاسبات والمعلومات - جامعة عين شمس
التوقيع/..... (مشرفا)
2. أ.د. نبيل إبراهيم هنداوى
الوظيفة/ أستاذ دكتور بقسم الفيزياء -كلية علوم – جامعه بنها
التوقيع/..... (عضوا)
3. أ.د. محمد إبراهيم العدوى
الوظيفة/ أستاذ دكتور بقسم هندسة الاتصالات والالكترونيات والحاسبات-كلية الهندسه-جامعه حلوان
التوقيع/..... (عضوا)

تاريخ البحث: / /

الدرسات العليا

اجيزت الرساله بتاريخ
/ /
موافقه مجلس الجامعه
/ /

ختم الاجازه
/ /
موافقه مجلس الكليه
/ /

التوصيف البصري لخلايا شمسية عالية الكفاءة ذات البنية النانومترية

الاسم: عمرو هشام خلف محمود
الدرجة العلمية: ماجستير فى علوم الفيزياء
القسم: الفيزياء
الكلية: العلوم
الجامعة: عين شمس
تاريخ التخرج: 2014 - جامعة عين شمس
تاريخ التسجيل: مارس / 2016
تاريخ المنحة: 2019

التوصيف البصري لخلايا شمسية عالية الكفاءة ذات البنية النانومترية

رساله مقدمه من
عمرو هشام خلف محمود
قسم الفيزياء
كلية العلوم - جامعة عين شمس

التوقيع

.....

.....

.....

المشرفون

د. هاله محمد حسني (رحمها الله)

استاذ مساعد متفرغ بقسم الفيزياء
كلية العلوم - جامعة عين شمس

د. محمد حسن عبد العزيز

استاذ مساعد بقسم العلوم الأساسية
كلية الحاسبات والمعلومات - جامعة عين شمس

د. محمد فرحات عثمان

استاذ مساعد بقسم الرياضيات و الفيزياء الهندسيه
كلية الهندسة - جامعة المنصورة

للحصول على درجة الماجستير في العلوم في الفيزياء

من كلية العلوم - جامعة عين شمس
قسم الفيزياء
(2019)

التوصيف البصري لخلايا شمسية عالية الكفاءة ذات البنية النانومترية

" رساله مقدمه للحصول على درجه للحصول على درجه الماجستير فى العلوم كجزء

مكمل لمتطلبات رساله الماجستير بكلية العلوم "

التخصص

علوم الفيزياء

اسم الباحث

عمرو هشام خلف محمود

بكالوريوس فيزياء 2014

اسماء المشرفين

د. هاله محمد حسني (رحمها الله)

استاذ مساعد متفرغ بقسم الفيزياء- كلية العلوم جامعة عين شمس

د. محمد حسن عبد العزيز

استاذ مساعد بقسم العلوم الأساسية- كلية الحاسبات والمعلومات - جامعة عين شمس

د. محمد فرحات عثمان

استاذ مساعد بقسم الرياضيات و الفيزياء الهندسيه - كلية الهندسة - جامعة المنصورة

جامعة عين شمس
كلية العلوم - قسم الفيزياء
(2019)